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D1.2 MATERIAL, COMPONENT AND CELL/MODULE TESTING PROTOCOLS

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PROJECT GENERAL INFORMATION

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DELIVERABLE GENERAL INFORMATION

Deliverable No.	D1.2 MATERIAL, COMPONENT AND CELL/MODULE TESTING PROTOCOLS
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1.2 GG	15/01/2205	Revision of G. Godillot (ARK)
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1.5	16/01/2024	Merged version with MK (v1.4) and GG (v1.2 GG) revisions
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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

WP	Work Package
AFF-SSB	Anode-Free Solid-State Battery
ALF	Aluminium Foil
BEV	Battery Electric Vehicle
CC	Constant Current
CCCV	Constant Current - Constant Voltage
DOD	Depth of Discharge
DUT	Device Under Test
EIS	Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy
EV	Electric Vehicle
GITT	Galvanostatic Intermittent Titration Technique
HEV	Hybrid Electric Vehicle
HSPE	Hybrid Solid Polymer Electrolyte
IEC	International Electrochemical Commission
IR	Infra-Red spectroscopy
LCC	Lithiophilic Current Collector
LiM-SSB	Lithium Metal Solid-State Battery
MLPC	Multilayer Pouch Cell
NMC	Lithium Nickel Manganese Cobalt oxides
SEM	Scanning Electron Microscopy
SEM-EDX	Scanning Electron Microscopy - Energy-Dispersive X-ray spectroscopy
SOC	State Of Charge
SS	Stainless Steel
STEM	Scanning Transmission Electron Microscopy
TEM	Transmission Electron Microscopy
TOF-SIMS	Time Of Flight – Secondary-Ion Mass Spectrometry
XPS	X-ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Deliverable 1.2 compiles all testing protocols for material and cell component characterization, as well as for evaluating the cell performance. Each test is detailed comprehensively to enable anyone consulting the deliverable to accurately reproduce the procedures and compare results with those obtained using SOLVE materials.

The testing protocols were defined by the partners involved in WP1, leveraging their expertise and roles within the project.

The protocols are categorized into different topics based on their application:

1. **Materials and cell components characterization**

- This section includes protocols for validating and studying all materials used in the preparation of hybrid solid polymer electrolytes (HSPE), and the positive and negative electrodes.

2. **Cell characterization**

- Various cell configurations will be used to assess the performance of the materials and technology developed in the SOLVE project. Cell configurations include symmetrical Lithium/Lithium for LiM-SSB, Lithiophilic current collector/lithium foil (lithium reservoir) for AF-SSB, SS/SS for ionic conductivity test and full cells with positive and negative electrodes. Tests will be conducted on cell formats ranging from coin cells to multi-layer pouch cells.

3. **Module characterization**

- This section presents tests to fully characterize the three modules assembled for the SOLVE project, examining both electrochemical and safety behavior.

4. **Post-Mortem analysis of materials**

- The protocols in this section aim to study cell components at the end of the cell life cycle. These studies will be crucial for understanding the aging and failure mechanisms of solid-state batteries.

All electrochemical tests are detailed in the Annex section of this document.

In conclusion, thanks to the fruitful collaboration of WP1 partners, we have defined a comprehensive collection of testing protocols for the characterization and study of solid-state batteries, from material conception to the end-of-life of the cell.

1. INTRODUCTION

The SOLVE project focuses on the development of solid-state batteries, encompassing everything from material conception to cell realization and characterization.

In Work Package 1 (WP1), all partners have defined specific testing procedures based on their expertise and roles within the project. These tests aim to characterize and validate the materials and cell components, study their electrochemical behavior, and assess performance in terms of safety. The data collected from these analyses will provide a deep understanding of how solid-state batteries work and how they can be further developed.

The testing protocols can be categorized as follows:

- **Physico-chemical characterization:** Validation of materials for cell component preparation.
- **Electrochemical performance:** Validation of cell components (positive electrode, polymer electrolyte, negative electrode) and assessment of full cell performance.
- **Safety tests:** Evaluation of the safety of the prototypes.
- **Post-mortem analysis:** Study and understanding of the failing mechanisms and determining the cell's end of life.

Various cell formats are used, ranging from coin cells to 10 Ah and 20 Ah pouch cells for AF- and LiM-SSB, respectively. This approach allows for the optimal format to be utilized at each phase of development. For instance, preliminary validation of cell components, such as the electrodes or the electrolyte, can be conducted using small cell formats. However, complete characterization of the full system requires larger formats, such as stacked pouch cells.

Additionally, safety tests for solid-state batteries must be performed using the largest available format to be more representative of the final cell required for specific applications. Therefore, these tests will be conducted using final pouch cells ranging from 5 to 20 Ah and in the final module.

1.1. DESCRIPTION OF TASK 1.3

Task 1.3 is dedicated to compiling all testing protocols employed within the SOLVE project. Building upon the project requirements outlined in T1.1 and the necessary characterization of materials, cell components, and final prototypes defined in T1.2. Task 1.3 has formulated comprehensive testing procedures. These procedures are designed to validate the technologies under development, specifically lithium metal solid-state batteries and anode-free solid-state batteries.

The process of developing SOLVE SSB has been meticulously mapped out, from material design and synthesis to cell and module performance. Precise testing protocols have been established in collaboration with the partners involved in WP1. All tests are thoroughly documented and made accessible to the entire consortium via the SOLVE' SharePoint.

Deliverable D1.2 consolidates all testing procedures, ensuring that experiments can be replicated accurately and comparably by any individual SOLVE partner.

1.1.1. TESTING PROTOCOLS ORGANIZATION AND REFERENCE

Testing procedures have been defined for each topic section: Materials and cell components, cell prototypes, modules, and post-mortem analysis.

Table 1 gathers each section with a brief description of the scope of the test.

Table 1: Sections scope of testing procedure.

Section	Scope of the test
Materials and cell components	Characterization and validation of hybrid solid polymer electrolyte, positive electrode obtained by wet and dry process, lithium metal negative electrode, and anode-free negative electrode.
Cell prototype	Electrochemical validation of all cell formats: coin cell, single layer pouch cells, small multilayer pouch cells (up to 1 Ah), final multilayer pouch cells (5 to 20 Ah). Safety assessment via abuse test.
Modules	Electrochemical validation. Safety assessment via abuse test.
Post-mortem analysis	Cell disassembly and material preparation procedure. Physical characterization. Data supplements evaluation of electrochemical performance.

Each testing protocol is named with a reference code explicating the WP(s) that will be using the protocol and a code according to the technology.

WP3-5_H2

In the example, the protocol details the testing procedure H2 that will be used by WP3 and 5.

All references written in bold green can be “*control+click*” to access directly the detailed protocol in the Annex section which contains all procedures.

1.1.2. TESTING PROTOCOLS RESPONDING TO SOLVE KPI

To fulfill the project's KPIs, SOLVE cells must meet precise specifications to enhance solid-state battery technology, making it suitable for a variety of applications.

The evaluation of generic and specific KPI will be performed by applying the most adapted testing protocols detailed in this document.

Table 2 gathers HORIZON-CL5-2023-D2-02-01 KPIs associated with the method, or the protocol reference number used to measure the target. All protocols are gathered in this document, either in the text or in the Annex section. “*Control+Click*” the reference on the right column to be redirected directly to the related testing protocol.

Table 2: Targets of HORIZON-CL5-2023-D2-02-01 call and protocols to evaluate them.

HORIZON-CL5-2023-D2-02-01	Target	Evaluation method or protocol reference
Usable Specific Energy	> 400 Wh/Kg	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> WP3-5_H1 Li-SSB (step 2) WP3-5_H4 AF-SSB (step 2)
Usable Energy Density	> 1000 Wh/L	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> WP3-5_H1 Li-SSB WP3-5_H4 AF-SSB
Cycle Life	3000 cycles at 50% DOD	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> WP3-5_H3 Li-SSB WP3-5_H6: AF-SSB
Cycle Life	> 500 cycles at 80% DOD	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> WP3-5_H2 Li-SSB WP3-5_H5: AF-SSB
Maximum Charge Rate	5C	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> WP3-5_L3
	10C	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> WP3-5_L5
Charge Time	< 20 min (ideally 15 min)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> WP3-5_L3 WP3-5_L5
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> WP5_M5 WP5_M6 WP5_M10
Safety: EUCAR Level	≤ 4	

In addition to meeting the HORIZON-CL5-2023-D2-02-01 call requirements, the SOLVE consortium has decided to extend the evaluation of the technology to include specific KPIs set by automotive and aviation end-users. All testing protocols related to these specific KPI are gathered in **Table 3**.

Table 3: End-users targets and protocols to evaluate them.

AUTOMOTIVE	Target	Evaluation method or protocol reference
Usable Specific Energy	> 400 Wh/Kg @BoL 90%SoC - C/3	Calculated with PROTEO according to capacity values obtained with protocols WP3-5_L1, WP3-5_L2: , WP3-5_L3
Usable Energy Density	> 1000 Wh/L @BoL 90%SoC - C/3	Calculated with PROTEO according to capacity values obtained with protocols WP3-5_L1, WP3-5_L2: , WP3-5_L3
Cycle Life	1000 cycles at C/3 - WLTP cycles, (EoL =80% SoH)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> WP3-5_L1 WP3-5_L2: WP3-5_L3
Maximum Charge Rate	5C	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> WP3-5_L3
Charge Time	< 10 min, 20-80% SOC	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> WP3-5_L3

Safety: EUCAR Level	≤ 4 RTCA DO	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • WP5_M5 • WP5_M6 • WP5_M9 •
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AVIATION	Target	Evaluation method or protocol reference
Usable Specific Energy	> 445 Wh/kg @BoL 15%SOC - 1C	• WP3-5_L4
Usable Energy Density	> 1350 Wh/L @BoL 90%SoC - C/3	• WP3-5_L4
Cycle Life	1000 cycles (Fast charge, fast discharge (school laps) (EoL = 0% SoH)	• WP3-5_L4
Maximum Charge Rate	10C for fast turn-around times	• WP3-5_L5
Charge Time	< 20 min 100% SOC	• WP3-5_L5
Safety	UN 38.3, EASA MOC-3 SC-VTOL	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 2.4.5.5.1 Overcharge* • 2.4.5.5.2 Overheat*

* Detailed testing protocols cannot be disclosed due to confidentiality. PVS will oversee the testing and share the results with the consortium.

2. PROTOCOLS

This chapter gathers the description of the following testing protocols:

- **Testing protocols for material and cell components characterization**
- **Testing protocols for cell characterization**
- **Testing protocols for module characterization**
- **Characterization techniques for post-mortem analysis of active cell materials**

As previously commented, for each topic, different types of testing will be employed:

- **Physico-chemical characterization**
- **Electrochemical characterization**
- **Abuse testing**
- **Postmortem analysis**

Depending on the aim of the test, different cell configurations can be used. The SOLVE project will use the following cell configurations:

- **Stainless steel – solid electrolyte separator – stainless steel (SS/SS)**
- **Lithium – solid electrolyte separator – aluminum or copper (Li/Al, Li/Cu)**
- **Lithium –solid electrolyte separator – lithium (Li/Li)**
- **Lithium –solid electrolyte separator – lithiophilic current collector (Li/LCC)**
- **Lithium –solid electrolyte separator – NMC cathode (Li/NMC)**
- **Lithiophilic current collector – solid electrolyte separator – NMC cathode (LCC/NMC)**

To access the detailed testing protocol in the Annex section, “*control+click*” the green bold reference in the text.

2.1. TESTING PROTOCOLS FOR MATERIALS AND CELL COMPONENTS CHARACTERIZATION

WP3 is set to develop and manufacture cell components for solid-state batteries using the advanced materials produced by WP2. The partners involved will focus on creating hybrid solid polymer electrolytes, high loading positive electrodes, lithium metal negative electrodes, and lithiophilic current collectors for anode-free technology.

The electrochemical characterization of the cell components will be done employing the following cell configurations:

- **Stainless steel – solid electrolyte separator – stainless steel (SS/SS)**
- **Lithium – solid electrolyte separator – aluminum or copper (Li/Al, Li/Cu)**
- **Lithium – solid electrolyte separator – lithium (Li/Li)**
- **Lithium – solid electrolyte separator – lithiophilic current collector (Li/LCC)**

For all configurations, different testing protocols have been defined to understand the material properties, the mechanisms behind cell behavior and how to improve electrochemical performance to fulfill the project targets.

2.1.1. CHARACTERIZATION OF THE HYBRID SOLID POLYMER ELECTROLYTE

SOLVE consortium partner POLITO design and synthesize innovative polymers for high-performance solid-state batteries. The laboratory-scale polymers and related formulations will be characterized by SOLVE partners according to the following analytical methods and testing protocols. Eventual variations to the presented methods will be specified in future deliverables and will be shared and agreed with all partners during follow-up meetings and general assemblies.

- **Coulometric Karl Fischer titration**

Coulometric Karl Fischer titration is used to determine water concentrations in solvents and ionic liquids prior to HSPE preparation using 899 KF coulometer (Metrohm) having a generator electrode with diaphragm. CombiCoulomat fritless (Merck) reagent is used for the analysis.

- **Melt viscosity (for further details consult ASTM D3835)**

This standard test method is suggested for determination of PVDF-HFP rheological properties by means of a capillary rheometer. Particularly, when carrying out compatibility tests among the several formulations where the PVDF-HFP might be submitted to thermal alterations. This test method covers measurement of the rheological properties of PVDF-HFP at a certain temperature or in a certain temperature range. This protocol covers measurements of melt viscosity, sensitivity, or stability, polymer memory, and shear sensitivity when extruding under constant rate or stress.

For the analysis, a capillary rheometer is used. The material to be tested is in form of pellets or powder. Material is loaded into the barrel of a capillary rheometer preheated to the testing temperature. After melting, the material is extruded at a constant volumetric flow rate. Typically, a range of flow rates is used, covering a shear rate range of 10/s-10,000/s.

The determination of the rheological behavior of the HSPE can differ from the abovementioned procedure and will be adapted choosing the best option according to HSPE's final properties.

- **Thermal stability by Thermogravimetric Analysis (TGA) and Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC)**

Thermal stability of electrolyte formulation is analyzed with thermogravimetric analysis and differential scanning calorimetry. These analyses are necessary for studying components compatibility and for characterizing the components phase changes, enthalpy at high temperatures and the time vs. temperature. The methods to be used depend on the material being tested and the requested assessment. In general, samples are packed at the bottom of a platinum crucible. The TGA is performed on a TGA/DSC thermoanalyzer by setting temperature range between 25 and 600 °C with a heating rate of 5 °C min⁻¹ under constant 100 ml·m⁻¹ nitrogen or oxygen flow.

After subtracting the base line from each sample curve, a sample weight monitoring on the TGA graph and the enthalpy monitoring on the DSC graph are obtained. The TGA curve provides information about sample weight losses.

This technique is also used to determine the crystallinity (T_c) of the samples with the following formula: $T_c (\%) = H_f / H_{fo} \times 100$, where H_{fo} is the polymer enthalpy 100% crystalline (104.7 J/g). The value of the enthalpy of the crystallization signal is recorded on the cooling curve. The maximum temperature to set is 200 °C, beyond this temperature, the sample begins to degrade, and this temperature is sufficient for comparisons with PVDF-HFP alone. The heating rate recommended is 10 °C/min.

In the case of HSPE, the specific protocols will be chosen according to the final properties of the material. All details will be shared in future deliverables and in the consortium meeting.

- **Physico-chemical Characterization of the HSPE**

For morphological and topological characterization of the HSPE, scanning electron microscopy (SEM) will be extensively used. Some good practices to keep in mind when analyzing polymeric materials:

- modulate the accelerating voltage (~10 kV) during SEM imaging,
- consider low electron beam time exposition,
- If possible, apply a gold coating (~3 nm) prior to the analysis.

For compositional quantitative analysis, energy dispersive x-ray spectrometry (EDX) is a technique that can be performed in parallel to SEM. Inorganic fillers within the sample can be effectively identified with EDX and their distribution within the polymer matrix can be determined by using the mapping tool of the setting program. The SEM parameters presented above apply also to this technique.

Another characterization technique that is suggested for quantitative analysis is nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR). ¹⁹F NMR provides information related to local ionic dynamics and diffusion coefficients in PVDF-HFP-based HSPE that can be correlated with conductivity behavior. Prior to the analysis, samples are dissolved in dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) or acetone at room temperature. The samples are analyzed on a Bruker AVANCE III 400 MHz instrument, at room temperature in ¹⁹F NMR. All measurements are performed under static conditions.

- PHFP content is calculated according to CF3 signals at -80 and -70 ppm,
- PVDF content is calculated according to CF2 signals between -122 and -85 ppm,
- FSI and TFSI content can be calculated according to F(SO₂) signals at 53 ppm and 80, respectively.

Once the obtention of the desired product is validated, the electrochemical properties of the HSPE will be evaluated. Its ionic conductivity and its electrochemical stability will be studied to assess their use with high voltage electrode or its ability to hinder dendrite growth according to the following testing protocols.

- **Stainless steel – solid electrolyte separator – stainless steel (SS/SS)**

- **Ionic conductivity**

The ionic conductivity of the resulting HSPEs is measured by electrochemical impedance spectroscopy using an impedance instrument, over the frequency range from 10 MHz to 1 Hz with an amplitude of 10 mV. The HSPE, with known diameter and thickness, is assembled between two stainless steel electrodes of 16 mm diameter in coin cell or Ecc-Std cells. The analysis can be carried out at fixed T (i. e. 25 °C) or scanning a range of temperatures.

The protocol defined for this analysis is the following:

WP2_A0: ionic conductivity

- **WP2_A0 – ionic conductivity**

- **Lithium – solid electrolyte separator – aluminum or copper (Li/Al, Li/Cu)**

- **Electrochemical oxidative (OX) and reductive (RED) stability by cyclic voltammetry (CV) and staircase voltammetry (SV)**

Cyclic Voltammetry (CV) and Staircase Voltammetry (SV) are used to study the electrochemical properties of materials, such as their redox behavior and stability under oxidative and reductive conditions. The measurements are carried out on a potentiostat (i.e. Bio-Logic). The samples are assembled in a hermetically sealed coin cell or Ecc-Std. The HSPE film (16 mm in diameter, max 18 mm) is placed between a lithium metal counter electrode (15 mm in diameter, max 18 mm) and an aluminum or copper working electrode (max 18 mm in diameter) for oxidation and reduction respectively.

For SV, first a rest period is held at 25 °C for at least 4 hours until a stable open circuit voltage is recorded (dV/dT limit 10 mV/h). In oxidation, the voltage is increased from 3 to 5 V vs. Li⁺/Li by steps of 100 mV, and the current response is recorded at the end of each step. In reduction, voltage is decreased from 2 to 0.01 V vs. Li⁺/Li by steps of 100 mV. Each step is held for 1 hour. EIS measurements are recommended before and after the SV. EIS measurement is carried out with an amplitude of 10 mV between 1 MHz and 100 mHz. For CV, the two protocols used for the tests are:

- **Lithium – solid electrolyte separator – Aluminum**
 - **WP2_D2: anodic stability window**
- **Lithium – solid electrolyte separator – Copper**
 - **WP2_D3: cathodic stability window**
- **Lithium – solid electrolyte separator – lithium (Li/Li)**

Coin cells and single layer pouch cells assembled with two lithium metal foils, serving as both the negative and positive electrodes separated by a solid electrolyte, will allow for the evaluation of the HSPE's stability against lithium, its ability to hinder Li dendrites growth, and prevent short circuits.

The protocols used for this study are the following:

- **WP2_A2 – critical current density – HSPE failure**
- **WP2_A4: interfacial stability**
- **WP2_C1 – transference number**

2.1.2. CHARACTERIZATION OF THE POSITIVE ELECTRODE

The positive electrodes are characterized by: (i) areal capacity calculation (ii) density analysis, (iii) morphological evaluation, and (iv) electrochemical characterization in coin cell and pouch cell format on the premises of CID.

- **Theoretical areal capacity calculation for positive electrode**

Measurement of areal capacity is carried out after initial drying of positive electrode slurry coatings on aluminum current collectors (CC). Four cathode discs of diameter 16.6 mm are cut from different areas of the dried cathode sheet with high precision EL-Cell dies. The discs are weighed using a high-precision weight balance with precision up to 5 decimal places.

The areal capacity of prepared cathode is calculated based on the area and weight of coating (weight of CC is excluded), cathode active material (CAM) content and the specific capacity of CAM material from the manufacturer.

- **Density calculation for positive electrode**

The density of prepared cathodes is calculated based on cathode mass loading and thickness of the calendared cathode sheets. Mass loading of cathode coating is calculated based on the weight and area of cathode coating detailed in the previous step. The thickness of calendared cathode sheets is measured using a digital micrometer with precision up to 3 decimals.

- **Morphological characterization of positive electrode**

The top-surface and cross-sectional morphology of prepared cathodes are characterized using scanning electron microscope with Schottky type-field emission gun source. The samples are mounted on aluminum pins using carbon tape to enable electron imaging. There are no additional conductive materials coated on the cathodes.

- **Electrochemical characterization of positive electrode**

Electrochemical characterization of the cathodes is done in both coin cell and pouch cell format. The protocols used for this study are the following:

Test in coin cell:

- **WP2_F1** – long-term cycling 100% DOD for coin cell
- **WP2-3_G1**: – floating test

Test in pouch cell:

- **WP3-5_H1** – long-term cycling 100% DOD
- **WP3-5_H2** – long-term cycling 80% DOD
- **WP3-5_H3** – long-term cycling 50% DOD
- **WP2-5_I1** – D-rate
- **WP2-5_I2**: – C-rate
- **WP2-5_I3** – symmetrical rate

2.1.3. CHARACTERIZATION OF THE NEGATIVE ELECTRODE

- **Morphological characterization of negative electrode**

SEM, cross-sectional SEM and SEM-EDX will be used for studying morphology of the surfaces as well as structures, compositions, and material distributions of the layers develop for lithium metal negative electrodes and current collectors (anode-free cell concept).

- **Electrochemical characterization of negative electrode**

Lithium metal negative electrode and lithiophilic current collectors will be screened and analyzed in Li/Li and Li/LCC cells according to different protocols.

- **Lithium – solid electrolyte separator – lithium (Li/Li)**

- **WP2_A1** – critical current density
- **WP2_A3** – critical current density – Li failure
- **WP2_B1, WP2_B2, WP2_B3** – depth of cycling
- **WP2-3_D1**: – corrosion current

- **Lithium – solid electrolyte separator – lithiophilic current collector (Li/LCC)**

For anode-free technology, the compatibility and performance of the lithiophilic current collector in contact with the solid electrolyte will be studied using the following protocol:

- **WP2_E1**: – screening test for lithiophilic current collector

2.2. TESTING PROTOCOLS FOR CELL CHARACTERIZATION

2.2.1. ELECTROCHEMICAL PERFORMANCE OF THE FULL CELL

Several testing protocols have been defined to fully assess the electrochemical performance of the systems. Tests performed in small format cells will be used to pre-assess the behavior of the systems and to determine cycling parameters such as the voltage window. Tests in larger scale cells will be used to assess properties such as cycle life according to standard and specific protocols for each application, storage, internal resistance during cycling, and more.

The two different technologies developed in SOLVE, Lithium Metal Solid-State Batteries and Anode-free Solid-State Batteries, will be studied using Li/NMC811 and LCC/NMC cell configurations.

- **Lithium – solid electrolyte separator – NMC811 cathode (Li/NMC811)**

Test in coin cells:

- **WP2_F1 – long-term cycling 100% DOD for coin cell**
- **WP2-3_G1: – floating test**

Test in pouch cells:

- **WP3-5_H1 – long-term cycling 100% DOD**
- **WP3-5_H2 – long-term cycling 80% DOD**
- **WP3-5_H3 – long-term cycling 50% DOD**
- **WP2-5_I1 – D-rate**
- **WP2-5_I2: – C-rate**
- **WP2-5_I3 – symmetrical rate**
- **WP2-5_I4 – calendar ageing**
- **WP3-5_L1 – standard cycling protocols for BEV**
- **WP3-5_L2: – drive protocols for BEV**
- **WP3-5_L3 – fast charge protocols for BEV**
- **WP3-5_L4 – C-rate and flight profile (school laps) aging test for EVTOL**
- **WP3-5_L5 – cycling protocol for high-rate battery for EVTOL**

- **Lithiophilic current collector – solid electrolyte separator – NMC cathode (LCC/NMC)**

For anode-free technology, cells will be studied in full configuration using coin cells, single-layer, and multi-layer pouch cells. These cells will be composed of a lithiophilic current collector, the HSPE separator, and the NMC positive electrode.

In this technology, the use of a higher cut-off voltage during the formation cycles is beneficial for the additional activation of the Li-rich cathode. Therefore, all protocols have been adapted, and the cut-off voltage during the formation cycle has been raised to 4.8 V.

The testing protocols are:

- **WP2_F2: – long-term cycling 100% DOD Coin cell**
- **WP3-5_H4 – long-term cycling 100% DOD**
- **WP3-5_H5: – long-term cycling 80% DOD**
- **WP3-5_H6: – long-term cycling 50% DOD**
- **WP2-5_H7: – D-rate**
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- **WP2-5_H8: – C-rate**
- **WP2-5_H9: – symmetrical rate**

2.2.2. ABUSE TESTING

The safety assessment of EV batteries is regulated by the *European Standard IEC 62660 – Part 3. The International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC)* is a global organization that promotes international cooperation on all questions concerning the standardization of EVs. Specifically, IEC 62660 outlines test procedures and acceptance criteria for the safety performance of secondary lithium-ion cells and cell blocks used for the propulsion of electric vehicles (EV), including battery electric vehicles (BEV) and hybrid electric vehicles (HEV).

In this context, all test procedures are detailed. When a test is included in IEC 62660, the standardized protocol will be applied. Non-standard tests will be performed in accordance with a specific protocol agreed upon by the SOLVE partners responsible for the safety assessment of the cells.

All safety tests are conducted using pouch cell formats. The response of a cell to an abuse test is closely related to its chemistry, size, and design. Therefore, it is preferable to perform safety tests on cell formats that closely resemble the final design. In the SOLVE project, all safety tests will be carried out on multi-layer pouch cells in larger formats (5 to 20 Ah) and in the final module.

- **General formation protocols for cell delivery for Li/NMC811 cells**

Cells for abuse testing will be formed according to the protocol established for Li-SSB and AF-SSB. The cells will be then charged to 30 % SOC and shipped to the partner in charge of abuse testing evaluation. Before testing the cells will be charged to 100 % SOC and tested according to the following protocols:

- **WP5_M1: – formation protocol for Li/NMC811 cells**
- **WP5_M2: – charging protocol from 30% to 100% SOC for Li/NMC811 cells**
- **WP5_M3 – charging protocol up to 30% SOC for LCC/NMC811 cells**
- **WP5_M4: – charging protocol from 30% to 100 % SOC for LCC/Li-rich NMC cells**

- **Overcharge according to IEC 62660**

The overcharge abuse test evaluates the cell's safety and performance when charged beyond its maximum voltage limit. This test simulates conditions that could lead to excessive internal pressure, overheating, and potential thermal runaway. Observations include voltage and temperature changes, gas release, swelling, and any signs of venting or ignition.

- **WP5_M5**

This test is performed to characterize cell responses to overcharge. The test shall be performed as follows.

1. Adjust the SOC of cell to 100% (protocols WP5_M2 or WP5_M3).
2. Continue charging the cell beyond the 100% SOC with charging current 1 It for BEV application and 5 It for HEV application at room temperature using a power supply sufficient to provide the constant charging current.

The overcharge test is discontinued when the voltage of cell reaches twice the maximum voltage specified by the manufacturer, or the quantity of electricity applied to the cell reaches 200% SOC equivalent.

The following data is measured and recorded as test results:

- *Cell voltage during the test,*
- *Cell current during the test,*
- *Cell temperature during the test.*

- **External short circuit according to IEC 62660**

The external short circuit abuse test assesses the cell's safety and performance when its terminals are directly connected, creating a short circuit. This test simulates conditions that could lead to rapid discharge and overheating. Observations include temperature rise, potential venting, and any signs of thermal runaway.

- **WP5_M6**

This test is performed to characterize cell responses to external short circuits. The test is performed as follows.

- 1) The SOC of cell is adjusted to 100% (protocols WP5_M2 or WP5_M3).
- 2) The cell is adjusted as in first step. Cell is stored at room temperature, and will be short-circuited by connecting the positive and negative terminals with an external resistance for 10 min. A total external resistance is equal to 5 mOhm or less as agreed previously between the customer and the manufacturer.

The following data is recorded as test results; The sample rate for voltage and current recording is 10 msec or less:

- *Cell voltage during the test,*
- *Cell current during the test,*
- *Cell temperature during the test,*
- *Total external resistance value.*

- **Mechanical penetration (SAE L2464)**

The nail penetration test is designed to evaluate the safety and mechanical integrity of the cell when subjected to a sharp object penetration. This test simulates conditions that could lead to internal short circuits and potential thermal runaway. Observations during the test include deformation, temperature changes, gas release, and possible ignition.

- **WP5_M7**

Test Description is based on SAE J2464. The Device Under Test (DUT) is penetrated with a mild steel (conductive) rod. The diameter of the rod, its end type, as well as the depth and rate of its penetration can be found in the following table. The orientation of penetration is perpendicular to the cell electrodes. The DUT should be observed for a minimum of 1 h after the test with the rod remaining in place.

Size of test object	Diameter of rod	Rod end type	Rate of penetration	Minimum depth of penetration
Cell	3 mm	Tapered to a sharp point	8 cm/s or greater	Through cell

The following data is collected as part of this test:

- Acceleration and the sudden forces exerted to the DUT case during nail penetration are measured with sensors with a minimum of 2 kHz bandwidth to assess the mechanical stresses and dynamic responses of the DUT.

- DUT deformation is determined by comparing measurements taken before and after the test to assess structural changes.
- The temperature of the DUT is recorded at several external and internal (where applicable) locations as a function of time to measure the thermal response during the test.
- Voltage and resistance of the DUT case with respect to the positive and negative terminals before and after the test to detect any electrical changes.
- Video monitoring during the test including the post-test observation period. Photographs of the test setup and the DUT, before and after the test are also included.

The results of tests specified shall be recorded with the descriptions:

Description	Effect
No effect	No effect. No change in appearance.
Deformation	Change or deformation in appearance including swelling.
Venting	Escape of liquid electrolyte from vent or venting with mist release.
Leakage	Escape of liquid electrolyte from a part except vent, such as casing, sealing part and/or terminals.
Smoking	Release of fume from vent.
Rupture	Mechanical failure of a cell container case induced by an internal or external cause, resulting in exposure or spillage but not ejection of materials. Including smoking at the rupture
Fire	Emission of flames from a cell.
Explosion	Failure that occurs when a cell container opens violently and major components are forcibly expelled.

- **Overheat up to thermal runaway**

An overheat test on a pouch cell involves gradually heating the cell to evaluate the thermal stability and safety of the cell under extreme conditions. During the test, several phenomena can be observed, including the onset of exothermic reactions, gas generation, swelling, venting, and potential ignition or explosion.

- **WP5_M8**

The cells will be received charged at 30 % SOC according to protocols WP5_M1 for lithium metal SSB or WP5_M3 for AFF-SSB.

The system's set-up is illustrated in **Figure 1**. Thermal probes are placed in contact with the pouch cell on both sides near the tabs and in the center of the cell. At least six probes are used to monitor temperature variation across different zones of the cell. The cell is heated by heating pads positioned on both sides of the pouch cell. The heaters are driven by a pilot probe located on the center of the pouch cell. This set-up is placed between two insulating layers to prevent heat dissipation to the external containment metallic plate or the environment.

The cell is charged to 100 % SOC according to protocols WP5_M2 and WP5_M4 for Li-SSB and AFF-SSB, respectively.

The cell is heated at a rate of 5 K/min \pm 2K until thermal runaway occurs. If no thermal event is recorded, the cell is heated to 300 °C and maintained at this temperature for 2 h.

In this specific case, no acceptance criteria are defined.

Figure 1: Set-up for overheat abuse test.

- **Overheat according to IEC 62660**

- **WP5_M9**

This test is performed to characterize cell responses to a high temperature environment. The test shall be performed as follows:

- 1) The SOC of cell is adjusted to 100 % for BEV application in accordance with protocols WP5_M2 or WP5_M3.
- 2) The cell, stabilized at room temperature, is placed in a gravity or circulating air convection oven. The oven temperature is raised at a rate of 5 K/min to a temperature of 130 °C ± 2 K. The cell shall remain at this temperature for 30 min before the test is discontinued.

- **ARC**

The Accelerating Rate Calorimetry (ARC) test evaluates the thermal stability and safety of a cell under controlled heating and adiabatic or quasi-adiabatic conditions. Unlike the overheat test, which rapidly heats the cell to induce thermal runaway, the ARC test uses slow gradual heating followed by a waiting/seek time where the system monitors and records each small spontaneous thermal response. Measures such as the rate of heat generated by exothermic reactions, the precise temperature related to each thermal event including onset of exothermic reactions, and thermal runaway can be obtained.

- **WP5_M10**

For this test, the cell is received at 30 % SOC (protocols WP5_M1 or WP5_M3) and charged at 100 % SOC according to protocols WP5_M2 and WP5_M4 respectively for Li-SSB and AFF-SSB.

The ARC test is performed in a quasi-adiabatic chamber heated at a controlled rate. The chamber is provided with sensors monitoring the temperature and pressure changes. The method applied is known as “Heat-Wait-Seek” (**Figure 2**).

The test starts in “Heat Mode” by heating up the cell in small temperature steps (5 K). At the end of each step, the “Wait Mode” is activated to reach thermal equilibrium. Then, the system enters “Seek Mode”, which seeks the temperature rate of change and ends with two possible modes: “Exotherm Mode” or “Heat Mode”. If the measured temperature rate of change is larger than the onset value (0.02 K/min), it means that the system is self-heating, thus the procedure passes into “Exotherm Mode”. In this quasi-adiabatic mode, the heaters in the calorimeter chamber immediately follow any change of the cell temperature, preventing the heat transfer to the chamber. Thus, it is heating up until a thermal runaway occurs or the chemicals are completely consumed by exothermic reactions. If the temperature rate of change falls below the onset value (0.02 K/min), the system goes back into “Heat Mode”.

Figure 2: Heat-Wait-Seek method for ARC test.

The test is carried out following the next configuration:

- Heat-wait-seek mode (HWS) method shall be used.
- Initial temperature: 30 °C.
- Temperature steps: 5 K.
- Waiting time between steps: 45 min.
- Maximum temperature: 305 °C.
- Temperature rate of change sensitivity: 0.02 K/min.
- Pressure: 1 atm.

2.3. TESTING PROTOCOLS FOR MODULE CHARACTERIZATION

Three modules of 60 Ah will be assembled in WP4 and delivered to WP5's partners for testing. The testing protocols detailed in this section aim to assess both the electrochemical performance and the safety of the module.

2.3.1. ELECTROCHEMICAL PERFORMANCE

The electrochemical performance of the module will be evaluated based on protocols from the ISO 12405 standard. The exact protocols for the testing of SSB module cannot be defined at this point, as they will depend on the module design (to be developed in Task T4.3 starting in M37) and the Battery Control Unit (BCU) that will manage the module's parameters. The selected protocols will be aligned with those used for cell electrochemical testing, particularly the long-term testing protocol.

2.3.2. ABUSE TESTING

At the time of writing this deliverable, the abuse testing protocols are still in progress, especially for aeronautical applications. RTCA DO-311A and DO-160G, which provides minimum operational performance standards and environmental conditions, and test procedures are mainly established based on battery systems that are designed for auxiliary powers such as APU. These battery systems contain low energy in comparison to a propulsion battery system that will be used for primary powertrains. Moreover, European Union Aviation Safety Agency (EASA) has established Means of Compliance with the Special Condition VTOL to identify the substantial progress that has been made in the development and integration of rechargeable lithium batteries with novel chemistries in aviation. Therefore, MOC-3 SC-VTOL along with DO-311A will be primarily used to access the thermal capabilities of SOLVE battery modules.

Battery Thermal Runaway Containment Test (RTCA DO-311A Paragraph 2.2.2.4) is performed by using one of the following test methods. Due to confidentiality, the details of each method won't be disclosed in this report. PVS, responsible for safety testing on module, will perform the testing and share the results with the consortium.

- *2.4.5.5.1 Test Method for Battery Thermal Runaway via Overcharging*
- *2.4.5.5.2 Test Method for Battery Thermal Runaway via Overheating*

In accordance with MOC-3 SC-VTOL Section 5(c) at least 20% of the cells in the battery system achieved thermal runaway in the test. In addition, the test guidelines that are given in section 7 shall be followed during the abuse test. The prevention of module-to-module thermal runaway propagation shall be achieved to characterize and validate the abuse test of the battery module during the thermal runaway non-propagation tests.

Due to the limited amount of battery modules that will be produced during this project, the abuse test is focused on thermal runaway propagation. Additional abuse tests such as short circuit, over discharge, and overcharge tests will be performed according to RTCA DO-311A standards. Due to confidentiality, the specifications for each test are not reported in this document. However, PVS, in charge of the testing, will apply the standard procedures and the data will be shared with SOLVE consortium.

2.4. CHARACTERIZATION TECHNIQUES FOR POST-MORTEM ANALYSIS OF MATERIALS

The post-mortem characterization of cells will be tuned to the needs of the consortium over the duration of the project, to ensure the relevant scientific questions regarding material-level changes that affect performance can be tackled. In terms of electrochemical protocols, the same protocols as described in previous sections will also be used to prepare samples for post-mortem analysis to stay relevant to the conditions of cycling and other tests. One additional step taken for the post-mortem analysis will be to investigate samples at different SoC in situations where SoC-dependence of measured parameters is expected. In this case, prior to cell disassembly, the SoC will be adjusted. Moreover, electrochemical analysis (impedance spectroscopy, GITT etc.) will also be performed before cell disassembly, where relevant.

After electrochemical stressing and testing, cells will be disassembled as necessary to enable techniques described in the next section. A variety of material preparation protocols will be employed, highly dependent on the technique to be used and the material itself.

Examples of the protocols include:

- 1) For SEM, cross-sectional SEM and SEM-EDX, a 5-10 nm conductive coating of amorphous carbon or gold will be used for the separator to enable electron imaging.
- 2) For (S)TEM, FIB-SEM lamella preparation with a cryo-airless workflow will be employed.
- 3) For XPS, no additional preparation of the samples is necessary.

The exact approach will be determined between the partners for specific post-mortem analysis.

2.4.1. PROTOCOL FOR POST-MORTEM POUCH CELL OPENING

- **Preparation of the cell before opening**

All cells used for post-mortem analysis must be fully discharged down to 2.8 V prior to opening. Once fully discharged, the cell will be transferred to an isolated area free from moisture and oxygen, such as a glove box/chamber, where it will be opened.

- **Work area for cell opening**

It is essential to ensure that the moisture and oxygen levels inside the glove box are appropriate, below 1 ppm in both cases (ideal: <0.1 ppm O₂ and <0.5 ppm humidity).

Ensure that only the tools necessary for opening the cell are present in the work area. All metallic surface, including tools such as tweezers, must be protected by electrical insulating material such as Kapton tape. Inert materials such as ceramics are preferred.

Verify the availability of a fire-resistant blanket or a container with Extover or pyro-bubbles (fire extinguishing agents) within the glove box to extinguish flames in case of fire. To enhance safety, ensure that a suitable fire extinguisher is available near the glove box.

A thermal camera must be available to check the cell temperature during handling.

- **Procedure for cell opening and handling of components**

The operator responsible for opening the cell must wear laboratory gloves over the gloves of the glove box for handling and opening of the cell. If the cell casing is rigid and/or might cause cuts during handling, cut-resistant gloves should be used as a precaution during the opening process.

It is advisable to place a tray or container under the cell in case of material or electrolyte leakage during the opening process, to prevent spreading.

Prior to any manipulation, the cell's tabs must be isolated with Kapton tape to avoid any external short-circuit. The cell is then open by making a cut along one of the sealed edges of the packaging (ALF material) using ceramic cutter/scissors to avoid potential short circuits. Then, the remaining edges will be cut, leaving the side of the cell with the tabs uncut. Once the welded joints of the tabs with the electrode current collector tabs are visible, they can be manually separated (or using ceramic tools) from the tabs.

IMPORTANT: Temperature must be monitored frequently. In case of temperature rise/fire, cover the cell with Extover/pyro-bubbles or, alternatively, with a fire-resistant blanket.

The components of the cell — casing and tabs, lithium electrodes, separators, and cathode electrodes — will be separated one by one, avoiding contact between the different components.

IMPORTANT: If lithium metal powder is detected, handle the electrodes carefully so that this powder remains in the tray to prevent spreading. Keep the cathodes separated from the rest of the cell components — casing, separator, and lithium metal — to avoid contact between lithium powder and cathode material, which could cause a fire. Collect all present lithium powder into a package, seal it, and label it for appropriate management as a special laboratory waste.

The ALF, tabs, and cell casing will be packed together. The remaining electrodes will be cleaned to remove salts from the electrolyte on their surface, if necessary.

For work involving solid electrolyte technology, the solvent used for cleaning the electrodes will be DMC (dimethyl carbonate) for electrodes with polymer gel residues.

To remove surface salts, it is sufficient to immerse the electrodes in the solvent for 1-2 minutes. The electrodes will be left to dry for 20-30 minutes to ensure complete evaporation of the solvent. Depending on the need for subsequent physicochemical/electrochemical characterization of the electrodes, one of the applied faces of the cathodes will be removed using NMP (N-methyl-2-pyrrolidone) solvent and left to dry for 30-60 minutes.

Once all components are clean, they will be packed separately (each component in a different package) and properly labelled for storage or further shipping.

2.4.2. CHARACTERIZATION OF MATERIALS

A range of characterization techniques are available and will be tailored to the specific questions of the consortium. Briefly, the techniques range from electrochemical (EIS, GITT, transient current measurements), through microscopies (SEM, STEM, optical microscopy, 3D optical and electron microscopy) to spectroscopies (XPS, ToF-SIMS) and diffraction (XRD, electron diffraction).

CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, the SOLVE project has meticulously compiled a comprehensive list of testing protocols for the characterization of the proposed solid state battery technologies. These protocols will be used during the project for the characterization of materials and cell components, as well as for the validation of the electrochemical performance of the cell components and the two cell technologies — lithium metal and anode-free solid-state batteries — across various cell formats, from symmetric coin cells to 20 Ah pouch cells and modules.

Moreover, the protocols are designed to facilitate post-mortem analysis, which is essential for gaining a deeper understanding of the chemical, physical, and electrochemical factors contributing to cell failure. Understanding cell failure is an important step in the learning cycle to develop these cells further.

All parameters of testing protocols are included in the Annex of this report. Additionally, specific protocols are accessible to all SOLVE partners via a dedicated folder on the SOLVE SharePoint, related to WP1 and T1.3.

This structured approach ensures that the SOLVE project can accurately and comparably replicate experiments, thereby advancing the development of solid-state battery technology.

3. ANNEXES

3.1. TESTING PROTOCOLS FOR SS/SS CELLS

WP2_A0: ionic conductivity

WP	2
Cell type	Li/Li
Cell format	EL-std
Protocol	WP2_A1

Stage	T, °C	Step	Mode	Test conditions			Cycles	
				A.C.V	Frequency range/time	Points/decade		
Pause	-20°C	0	Rest	Open circuit		3 h	-	
EIS	-20°C	1	EIS	PEIS	20 mV	300000-1Hz	12	3 cycles
			Rest	Open circuit		5 min	-	
Pause	-10°C	2	Rest	Open circuit		120 min	-	
EIS	-10°C	3	EIS	PEIS	20 mV	300000-1Hz	12	3 cycles
			Rest	Open circuit		5 min	-	
Pause	0°C	4	Rest	Open circuit		120 min	-	
EIS	0°C	5	EIS	PEIS	20 mV	300000-1Hz	12	3 cycles
			Rest	Open circuit		5 min	-	
Pause	10°C	6	Rest	Open circuit		120 min	-	
EIS	10°C	7	EIS	PEIS	20 mV	300000-1Hz	12	3 cycles
			Rest	Open circuit		5 min	-	
Pause	20°C	8	Rest	Open circuit		120 min	-	
EIS	20°C	9	EIS	PEIS	20 mV	300000-1Hz	12	3 cycles
			Rest	Open circuit		5 min	-	
Pause	30°C	10	Rest	Open circuit		120 min	-	
EIS	30°C	11	EIS	PEIS	20 mV	300000-1Hz	12	3 cycles
			Rest	Open circuit		5 min	-	
Pause	40°C	12	Rest	Open circuit		120 min	-	
EIS	40°C	13	EIS	PEIS	20 mV	300000-1Hz	12	3 cycles
			Rest	Open circuit		5 min	-	
Pause	50°C	14	Rest	Open circuit		120 min	-	
EIS	50°C	15	EIS	PEIS	20 mV	300000-1Hz	12	3 cycles
			Rest	Open circuit		5 min	-	
Pause	60°C	16	Rest	Open circuit		120 min	-	
EIS	60°C	17	EIS	PEIS	20 mV	300000-1Hz	12	3 cycles

			Rest	Open circuit		5 min	-	
Pause	70°C	18	Rest	Open circuit		120 min	-	
EIS	70°C	19	EIS	PEIS	20 mV	300000-1Hz	12	3 cycles
			Rest	Open circuit		5 min	-	
Pause	80°C	20	Rest	Open circuit		120 min	-	
EIS	80°C	21	EIS	PEIS	20 mV	300000-1Hz	12	3 cycles
			Rest	Open circuit		5 min	-	

3.2. TESTING PROTOCOLS FOR LI/LI CELLS

WP2_A1: critical current density

WP	2
Cell type	Li/Li
Cell format	Coin cells
Protocol	WP2_A1

Stage	T, °C	Step	Mode	Current density (mA/cm ²)	Termination conditions		Cycles	
					Time	Voltage, V		
Safety limits						>5		
Pause	25	0	Rest	Open circuit		12 h		
Galvanostatic cycling	25	1	Charge	CC	0.02	1 h	Max +2V	5 cycles
			Rest	Open circuit		5 min		
			Discharge	CC	0.02	1 h	Min -2 V	
			Rest	Open circuit		5 min		
Galvanostatic cycling	25	2	Charge	CC	0.05	1 h	Max +2V	5 cycles
			Rest	Open circuit		5 min		
			Discharge	CC	0.05	1 h	Min -2 V	
			Rest	Open circuit		5 min		
Galvanostatic cycling	25	3	Charge	CC	0.1	1 h	Max +2V	5 cycles
			Rest	Open circuit		5 min		
			Discharge	CC	0.1	1 h	Min -2 V	
			Rest	Open circuit		5 min		
Galvanostatic cycling	25	4	Charge	CC	0.25	1 h	Max +2V	5 cycles
			Rest	Open circuit		5 min		
			Discharge	CC	0.25	1 h	Min -2 V	
			Rest	Open circuit		5 min		
Galvanostatic cycling	25	5	Charge	CC	0.5	1 h	Max +2V	5 cycles
			Rest	Open circuit		5 min		
			Discharge	CC	0.5	1 h	Min -2 V	
			Rest	Open circuit		5 min		

Galvanostatic cycling	25	6	Charge	CC	0.75	1 h	Max +2V	5 cycles
			Rest	Open circuit		5 min		
			Discharge	CC	0.75	1 h	Min -2 V	
			Rest	Open circuit		5 min		
Galvanostatic cycling	25	7	Charge	CC	1	1 h	Max +2V	5 cycles
			Rest	Open circuit		5 min		
			Discharge	CC	1	1 h	Min -2 V	
			Rest	Open circuit		5 min		
Galvanostatic cycling	25	8	Charge	CC	2	1 h	Max +2V	5 cycles
			Rest	Open circuit		5 min		
			Discharge	CC	2	1 h	Min -2 V	
			Rest	Open circuit		5 min		
Galvanostatic cycling	25	9	Charge	CC	3	1 h	Max +2V	5 cycles
			Rest	Open circuit		5 min		
			Discharge	CC	3	1 h	Min -2 V	
			Rest	Open circuit		5 min		
Galvanostatic cycling	25	10	Charge	CC	4	1 h	Max +2V	5 cycles
			Rest	Open circuit		5 min		
			Discharge	CC	4	1 h	Min -2 V	
			Rest	Open circuit		5 min		
Galvanostatic cycling	25	11	Charge	CC	5	1 h	Max +2V	5 cycles
			Rest	Open circuit		5 min		
			Discharge	CC	5	1 h	Min -2 V	
			Rest	Open circuit		5 min		

WP2_A2: critical current density – HSPE failure

WP	2
Cell type	Li/Li
Protocol	WP2_A2

CCD determination -
HSPE failure Li 60 μm

Stage	T, oC	Step	Mode	Acquisition				Termination conditions		
				Time (s)	Voltage (mV)	Current (mA)	Current density (mA/cm ²)	Time	Voltage, V	Capacity (mAh/cm ²)
Safety limits									>5	
Pause	25	0	Rest	Open circuit	30	5			12 h	
CCD	25	1	I >0	CC	30	5	0.025	NA		0.5
			Rest	Open circuit	30	5		1h		
CCD	25	2	I >0	CC	30	5	0.05	NA		0.5
			Rest	Open circuit	30	5		1h		
CCD	25	3	I >0	CC	30	5	0.1	NA		0.5
			Rest	Open circuit	30	5		1h		
CCD	25	4	I >0	CC	30	5	0.25	NA		0.5
			Rest	Open circuit	30	5		1h		
CCD	25	5	I >0	CC	30	5	0.5	NA		0.5
			Rest	Open circuit	30	5		1h		
CCD	25	6	I >0	CC	30	5	0.75	NA		0.5
			Rest	Open circuit	30	5		1h		
CCD	25	7	I >0	CC	30	5	1	NA		0.5
			Rest	Open circuit	30	5		1h		
CCD	25	8	I >0	CC	30	5	1.5	NA		0.5
			Rest	Open circuit	30	5		1h		
CCD	25	9	I >0	CC	30	5	2	NA		0.5
			Rest	Open circuit	30	5		1h		
CCD	25	10	I >0	CC	30	5	2.5	NA		0.5
			Rest	Open circuit	30	5		1h		
CCD	25	11	I >0	CC	30	5	3	NA		0.5
			Rest	Open circuit	30	5		1h		
CCD	25	12	I >0	CC	30	5	3.5	NA		0.5
			Rest	Open circuit	30	5		1h		
CCD	25	13	I >0	CC	30	5	4	NA		0.5
			Rest	Open circuit	30	5		1h		

WP2_A3: critical current density – Li failure

WP	2
Cell type	Li/Li
Protocol	WP2_A3

CCD determination - Li failure
Li 5 μm

Stage	T, oC	Step	Mode	Acquisition				Termination conditions		
				Time (s)	Voltage (mV)	Current (mA)	Current density (mA/cm ²)	Time	Voltage, V	Capacity (mAh/cm ²)
Safety limits									>5	
Pause	25	0	Rest	Open circuit	30	5			12 h	
CCD	25	1	>0	CC	30	5	0.025	NA		0,07
CCD	25	2	>0	CC	30	5	0.05	NA		0,07
CCD	25	3	>0	CC	30	5	0.1	NA		0,07
CCD	25	4	>0	CC	30	5	0.25	NA		0,07
CCD	25	5	>0	CC	30	5	0.5	NA		0,07
CCD	25	6	>0	CC	30	5	0.75	NA		0,07
CCD	25	7	>0	CC	30	5	1	NA		0,07
CCD	25	8	>0	CC	30	5	1,5	NA		0,07
CCD	25	9	>0	CC	30	5	2	NA		0,07
CCD	25	10	>0	CC	30	5	2,5	NA		0,07
CCD	25	11	>0	CC	30	5	3	NA		0,07
CCD	25	12	>0	CC	30	5	3,5	NA		0,07
CCD	25	13	>0	CC	30	5	4	NA		0,07

WP2_A4: interfacial stability

WP	2
Cell type	Li/Li
Cell format	Coin cells*
Protocol	WP2_A4

*also Ecc-Std cells

Stage	T, °C	Step	Mode	Test condition			Cycles	
				A.C.V	Frequency range/time	Points/decade		
Pause	25°C	0	Rest	Open circuit		3 h		
EIS	25°C	1	EIS	PEIS	20 mV	300000-1Hz	12	6 cycles
			Rest	Open circuit		120 min		
EIS	25°C	1	EIS	PEIS	20 mV	300000-1Hz	12	14 cycles
			Rest	Open circuit		12 h		

WP2_B1: depth of cycling 0.1 mAh/cm²

WP	2
Cell type	Li/Li
Cell format	Coin cells
Protocol	WP2_B1

Depth of Cycling/Areal capacity

0.1 mAh/cm²

Stage	T, °C	Step	Mode	Control	Termination conditions		Cycles
				Current density (mA/cm ²)	Time	Voltage, V	
Safety limits						>5	
Pause	25	0	Rest	Open circuit		12 h	
Galvanostatic cycling	25	1	Charge	CC	0.1	1 h	1000 cycles
			Rest	Open circuit		5 min	
			Discharge	CC	0.1	1 h	
			Rest	Open circuit		5 min	

WP2_B2: depth of cycling 1 mAh/cm²

WP	2
Cell type	Li/Li
Cell format	Coin cells
Protocol	WP2_B2

Depth of Cycling/Areal capacity

1 mAh/cm²

Stage	T, °C	Step	Mode	Control	Termination conditions		Cycles
				Current density (mA/cm ²)	Time	Voltage, V	
Safety limits						>5	
Pause	25	0	Rest	Open circuit		12 h	
Galvanostatic cycling	25	1	Charge	CC	0.1	10 h	1000 cycles
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min	
			Discharge	CC	0.1	10 h	
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min	

WP2_B3: depth of cycling 4 mAh/cm²

WP	2
Cell type	Li/Li
Cell format	Coin cells
Protocol	WP2_B3

Depth of Cycling/Areal capacity

4 mAh/cm²

Stage	T, °C	Step	Mode	Control	Termination conditions		Cycles
				Current density (mA/cm ²)	Time	Voltage, V	
Safety limits						>5	
Pause	25	0	Rest	Open circuit		12 h	
Galvanostatic cycling	25	1	Charge	CC	0.1	40 h	1000 cycles
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min	
			Discharge	CC	0.1	40 h	
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min	

WP2_C1: Li+ transference number

WP	2
Cell type	Li/Li
Protocol	WP2_C1

T+ measurement

* Parameters can be tuned. PEIS amplitude from 10 mV to 30 mV.

CA polarization from 10 mV to 50 mV

Stage	T, °C	Step	Mode	Acquisition				Termination conditions		
				Time (s)	Voltage (mV)	Pts / decade	Amplitude (mV)*	Time	Voltage, V	Capacity (mAh/cm ²)
Safety limits										
Pause	25	0	Rest	Open circuit	30	5	NA	NA	12 h	
			PEIS			10	10			
			Chronoamperometry (CA)	Early beginning: 0,1 After: 10 s			10	steady state		
			PEIS			10	10			

WP2-3_D1: corrosion current

WP	2
Cell type	Li/Li
Protocol	WP2-3_D1

Corrosion current

Stage	T, °C	Step	Mode	Acquisition				Termination conditions		
				Time (s)	Voltage (mV)		dE/dt (mV/min)	Time	Voltage, V	Capacity (mAh/cm ²)
Safety limits										
Pause	25	0	Rest	Open circuit	30	5			12 h	
				Tafel plot	30	5		1		-0,1 to 0,1

3.3. TESTING PROTOCOLS FOR LI/AL CELLS

WP2_D2: anodic stability window

WP	2
Cell type	Li/Al*
Cell format	Ecc-Std
Protocol	WP2_D2

* Carbon coated Al will be also used

Stage	T, °C	Step	Mode	Test condition			Cycles
				Initial voltage (V)	Final voltage (V)	Scan rate (mV/s)	
Pause	25	0	Rest	Open circuit		3 h	
CV	25	1	CV	oxidation	OCV	5	0.1
		2	CV	reduction	5	Initial voltage	0.1

3.4. TESTING PROTOCOLS FOR LI/CU CELLS

WP2_D3: cathodic stability window

WP	2
Cell type	Li/Cu
Cell format	Ecc-Std
Protocol	WP2_D3

Stage	T, °C	Step	Mode	Test condition			Cycles
				Initial voltage (V)	Final voltage (V)	Scan rate (mV/s)	
Pause	25	0	Rest	Open circuit		3 h	
CV	25	1	CV	oxidation	OCV	-0.5	0.1
		2	CV	reduction	-0.5	Initial voltage	0.1

3.5. TESTING PROTOCOLS FOR LI/LCC CELLS

WP2_E1: screening test for lithophilic current collector

WP	2	Screening test for lithophilic current collector Assuming critical current density - Lithium foil reservoir ≥ 10 mAh/cm ² (Thickness - 50 μ m) 0.25 mA/cm ²
Cell type	Li/LCC	
Cell format	Coin cells	
Protocol	WP2_E1	

Stage	T, °C	Step	Mode	Control conditions				Termination conditions			Cycles	
				Time	Voltage, V	Current (mA)	Current density (mA/cm ²)	Time	Voltage, V	Current		
Safety limits									>5			
Pause	25	0	Rest	Open circuit					12 h			
Lithium deposition step	25	1	Discharge (negative current)	CC			0.25		20 h			1 cycle
			Rest	Open circuit					5 min			
Galvanostatic cycling phase	25	2	Charge (Positive current)	CC			0.25		14 h	1V		20 cycles
			Rest	Open circuit					5 min			
			Discharge (negative current)	CC			0.25		14 h			
			Rest	Open circuit					5 min			
Final Lithium stripping step	25	3	Charge (Positive current)	CC			0.25		20 h	1V		1 cycle
			Rest	Open circuit					5 min			
Loop	25	4	Go back to step 1									

3.6. TESTING PROTOCOLS FOR LI/NMC CELLS

- Lithium – solid electrolyte separator – NMC cathode (Li/NMC)

WP2_F1: long-term cycling 100% DOD for coin cell

WP	2
Cell type	Li/NMC 811
Cell format	Coin cells
Protocol	WP2_F1

Long-term cycling - Till
CR<75%

DOD – 100%

Stage	T, °C	Step	Mode	Control conditions			Termination conditions			Cycles
				Time	Voltage, V	Current, C-rate	Time	Voltage, V	Current	
Safety limits								<2.45, >4.5		
Pause	25	0	Rest	Open circuit			12 h			
Galvanostatic cycling	25	1	Charge	CCCV		0.05	26 h	4.4	0.025	3000
			Rest	Open circuit			10 min			
			Discharge	CC		0.1		2.8		
			Rest	Open circuit			10 min			

WP2-3_G1: floating test

WP	2
Cell type	Li/NMC 811
Cell format	Coin cells
Protocol	WP2-3_G1

Electrochemical Float test - Till 5V

Stage	T, °C	Step	Mode	Control conditions			Termination conditions			Cycles
				Time	Voltage, V	Current, C-rate	Time	Voltage, V	Current	
Safety limits								<2.45, >5.1		
Pause	25	0	Rest	Open circuit			12 h			
Floating test	25	1	Charge	CCCV		0.05		4.2		
		2	Charge	CV			1 h	4.2		
		3	Charge	CV			1 h	4.3		
		4	Charge	CV			1 h	4.4		
		5	Charge	CV			1 h	4.5		
		6	Charge	CV			1 h	4.6		
		7	Charge	CV			1 h	4.7		
		8	Charge	CV			1 h	4.8		
		9	Charge	CV			1 h	4.9		
		10	Charge	CV			1 h	5.0		

		11	Rest	Open circuit			10 min			
			Discharge	CC		0.1		2.8		

WP3-5_H1: long-term cycling 100% DOD

WP	WP3-5	Standard cycling protocol
Cell type	Li/NMC811	
Cell format	MLPC	
Protocol I	WP3-5_H1	Long-term cycling 100% DOD - Till CR<75% + formation + initial check-up + check-up cycle and IR check

Stage	T, °C	Step	Mode	Control	Termination conditions			Cycles	
				Current, C	Time	Voltage, V	Current		
Safety limits						<2.45, >4.5			
Pause	25	0	Rest	Open circuit		12 h			
Formation	25	1	Charge	CCCV	0.05	26 h	4.4	0.025	2
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min			
			Discharge	CC	0.05	20 h	2.8		
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min			
Check-up	25	2	Charge	CCCV	0.05	20 h	4.4	0.025	Capacity
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min			
			Discharge	CC	0.1	10 h	2.8		
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min			
Check-up	25	3	Charge	CCCV	0.05	20 h	4.4	0.025	IR
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min			
			Discharge	CC	0.1	2.5 h	25% SOD		
			Discharge	CC	0.2	30 sec			
			Rest	Open circuit		30 sec			
			Discharge	CC	0.1	2.5 h	50% SOD		
			Discharge	CC	0.2	30 sec			
			Rest	Open circuit		30 sec			
			Discharge	CC	0.1	2.5 h	75% SOD		
			Discharge	CC	0.2	30 sec			
			Rest	Open circuit		30 sec			
			Discharge	CC	0.1	2.5 h	2.8		
Check-up	25	4	Charge	CC	0.05	6 h	3.85		Self discharge
			Rest	Open circuit		24 h			
			Discharge	CC	0.1	10 h	2.8		
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min			
Cycling 100% DOD	25	5	Charge	CCCV	0.05	20 h	4.4	0.025	50
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min			

			Discharge	CC	0.1	10 h	2.8	
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min		
Loop	25	6	Go back to step 2 each 50 cycles					

WP3-5_H2: long-term cycling 80% DOD

WP	WP3-5	SAFT' standard cycling protocol
Cell type	Li/NMC811	
Cell format	MLPC	
Protocol	WP3-5_H2	Long-term cycling 80% DOD (100%-20% SOC) - Till CR<75% + formation + initial check-up + check-up cycle and IR check

Stage	T, °C	Step	Mode	Control	Termination conditions			Cycles	
				Current, C	Time	Voltage, V	Current		
Safety limits						<2.45, >4.5			
Pause	25	0	Rest	Open circuit		12 h			
Formation	25	1	Charge	CCCV	0.05	26 h	4.4	0.025	2
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min			
			Discharge	CC	0.05	20 h	2.8		
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min			
Check-up	25	2	Charge	CCCV	0.05	20 h	4.4	0.025	Capacity
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min			
			Discharge	CC	0.1	10 h	2.8		
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min			
Check-up	25	3	Charge	CCCV	0.05	20 h	4.4	0.025	IR
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min			
			Discharge	CC	0.1	2.5 h	25% SOD		
			Discharge	CC	0.2	30 sec			
			Rest	Open circuit		30 sec			
			Discharge	CC	0.1	2.5 h	50% SOD		
			Discharge	CC	0.2	30 sec			
			Rest	Open circuit		30 sec			
			Discharge	CC	0.1	2.5 h	75% SOD		
			Discharge	CC	0.2	30 sec			
			Rest	Open circuit		30 sec			
			Discharge	CC	0.1	2.5 h	2.8		
Check-up	25	4	Charge	CC	0.05	6 h	3.85		Self discharge
			Rest	Open circuit		24 h			
			Discharge	CC	0.1	10 h	2.8		
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min			
	25	5	Charge	CCCV	0.05	20 h	4.4	0.025	50

Cycling 80% DOD			Rest	Open circuit		10 min		
			Discharge	CC	0.1	10 h	3.76	
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min		
Loop	25	6	Go back to step 2 each 50 cycles					

WP3-5_H3: long-term cycling 50% DOD

WP	WP3-5
Cell type	Li/NMC 811
Cell format	MLPC
Protocol	WP3-5_H3

Standard cycling protocol

Long-term cycling 50% DOD (70%-20% DOD) - Till CR<75% + formation + initial check-up + check-up cycle and IR check

Stage	T, °C	Step	Mode	Control	Termination conditions			Cycles	
				Current, C	Time	Voltage, V	Current		
Safety limits						<2.45, >4.5			
Pause	25	0	Rest	Open circuit		12 h			
Formation	25	1	Charge	CCCV	0.05	26 h	4.4	0.025	2
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min			
			Discharge	CC	0.05	20 h	2.8		
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min			
Check-up	25	2	Charge	CCCV	0.05	20 h	4.4	0.025	Capacity
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min			
			Discharge	CC	0.1	10 h	2.8		
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min			
Check-up	25	3	Charge	CCCV	0.05	20 h	4.4	0.025	IR
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min			
			Discharge	CC	0.1	2.5 h	25% SOD		
			Discharge	CC	0.2	30 sec			
			Rest	Open circuit		30 sec			
			Discharge	CC	0.1	2.5 h	50% SOD		
			Discharge	CC	0.2	30 sec			
			Rest	Open circuit		30 sec			
			Discharge	CC	0.1	2.5 h	75% SOD		
			Discharge	CC	0.2	30 sec			
			Rest	Open circuit		30 sec			
			Discharge	CC	0.1	2.5 h	2.8		
Check-up	25	4	Charge	CC	0.05	6 h	3.85		Self discharge
			Rest	Open circuit		24 h			
			Discharge	CC	0.1	10 h	2.8		

			Rest	Open circuit		10 min			
Cycling 50% DOD	25	5	Charge	CCCV	0.05	20 h	4.16	0.025	50
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min			
			Discharge	CC	0.1	10 h	3.76		
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min			
Loop	25	6	Go back to step 2 each 50 cycles						

WP2-5_I1: D-rate

WP	2-5
Cell type	Li/NMC8 11
Cell format	MLPC
Protocol	WP2- 5_I1

D rate: formation + initial check-up + IR
+ D-rate test

Stage	T, °C	Step	Mode	Control	Termination conditions			Cycles	
				Current, C	Time	Voltage, V	Current		
Safety limits						<2.45, >5.1			
Pause	25	0	Rest	Open circuit		12 h			
Formation	25	1	Charge	CCCV	0.05	26 h	4.4	0.025	2
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min			
			Discharge	CC	0.05	20 h	2.8		
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min			
Check-up	25	2	Charge	CCCV	0.05	20 h	4.4	0.025	Capacity
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min			
			Discharge	CC	0.1	10 h	2.8		
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min			
Check-up	25	3	Charge	CCCV	0.05	20 h	4.4	0.025	IR
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min			
			Discharge	CC	0.1	2.5 h	25% SOD		
			Discharge	CC	0.2	30 sec			
			Rest	Open circuit		30 sec			
			Discharge	CC	0.1	2.5 h	50% SOD		
			Discharge	CC	0.2	30 sec			
			Rest	Open circuit		30 sec			
			Discharge	CC	0.1	2.5 h	75% SOD		
			Discharge	CC	0.2	30 sec			
			Rest	Open circuit		30 sec			
			Discharge	CC	0.1	2.5 h	2.8		
Check-up	25	4	Charge	CC	0.05	6 h	3.85		Self discharge
			Rest	Open circuit		24 h			

			Discharge	CC	0.1	10 h	2.8			
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min				
D-Rate	25	5	Charge	CCCV	0.05	26 h	4.4	0.025		
		6	Rest	Open circuit		10 min				
		7	Discharge	CC	0.1	10 h	2.8			
		8	Rest	Open circuit		10 min				
		9	Charge	CCCV	0.05	26 h	4.4	0.025		
		10	Rest	Open circuit		10 min				
		11	Discharge	CC	0.2	5 h	2.8			
		12	Rest	Open circuit		10 min				
		13	Charge	CCCV	0.05	26 h	4.4	0.025		
		14	Rest	Open circuit		10 min				
		15	Discharge	CC	0.5	2 h	2.8			
		16	Rest	Open circuit		10 min				
		17	Charge	CCCV	0.05	26 h	4.4	0.025		
		18	Rest	Open circuit		10 min				
		19	Discharge	CC	1	1 h	2.8			
		20	Rest	Open circuit		10 min				
		21	Charge	CCCV	0.05	26 h	4.4	0.025		
		22	Rest	Open circuit		10 min				
		23	Discharge	CC	2	30 min	2.8			
		24	Rest	Open circuit		10 min				
		25	Charge	CCCV	0.05	26 h	4.4	0.025		
		26	Rest	Open circuit		10 min				
		27	Discharge	CC	1	1 h	2.8			
		28	Rest	Open circuit		10 min				
		29	Charge	CCCV	0.05	26 h	4.4	0.025		
		30	Rest	Open circuit		10 min				
		31	Discharge	CC	0.5	2 h	2.8			
		32	Rest	Open circuit		10 min				
		33	Charge	CCCV	0.05	26 h	4.4	0.025		
		34	Rest	Open circuit		10 min				
		35	Discharge	CC	0.2	5 h	2.8			
		36	Rest	Open circuit		10 min				
		37	Charge	CCCV	0.05	26 h	4.4	0.025		
		38	Rest	Open circuit		10 min				
		39	Discharge	CC	0.1	10 h	2.8			
		40	Rest	Open circuit		10 min				
		Loop	25	41	Go back to step 2 until 4					

WP2-5_I2: C-rate

WP	2-5
Cell type	Li/NMC811
Cell format	MLPC
Protocol	WP2-5_I2

C rate: formation + initial check-up + IR + C-rate test

Stage	T, °C	Step	Mode	Control	Termination conditions			Cycles	
				Current, C	Time	Voltage, V	Current		
Safety limits						<2.45, >5.1			
Pause	25	0	Rest	Open circuit		12 h			
Formation	25	1	Charge	CCCV	0.05	26 h	4.4	0.025	2
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min			
			Discharge	CC	0.05	20 h	2.8		
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min			
Check-up	25	2	Charge	CCCV	0.05	20 h	4.4	0.025	Capacity
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min			
			Discharge	CC	0.1	10 h	2.8		
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min			
Check-up	25	3	Charge	CCCV	0.05	20 h	4.4	0.025	IR
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min			
			Discharge	CC	0.1	2.5 h	25% SOD		
			Discharge	CC	0.2	30 sec			
			Rest	Open circuit		30 sec			
			Discharge	CC	0.1	2.5 h	50% SOD		
			Discharge	CC	0.2	30 sec			
			Rest	Open circuit		30 sec			
			Discharge	CC	0.1	2.5 h	75% SOD		
			Discharge	CC	0.2	30 sec			
			Rest	Open circuit		30 sec			
			Discharge	CC	0.1	2.5 h	2.8		
Rest	Open circuit		10 min						
Check-up	25	4	Charge	CC	0.05	6 h	3.85		Self discharge
			Rest	Open circuit		24 h			
			Discharge	CC	0.1	10 h	2.8		
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min			
C-Rate	25	5	Charge	CC	0.05	20 h	4.4		
		6	Rest	Open circuit		10 min			
		7	Discharge	CC	0.1	10 h	2.8		
		8	Rest	Open circuit		10 min			
		9	Charge	CC	0.1	10 h	4.4		
		10	Rest	Open circuit		10 min			

		11	Discharge	CC	0.1	10 h	2.8				
		12	Rest	Open circuit		10 min					
		13	Charge	CC	0.2	5 h	4.4				
		14	Rest	Open circuit		10 min					
		15	Discharge	CC	0.1	10 h	2.8				
		16	Rest	Open circuit		10 min					
		17	Charge	CC	0.5	2 h	4.4				
		18	Rest	Open circuit		10 min					
		19	Discharge	CC	0.1	10 h	2.8				
		20	Rest	Open circuit		10 min					
		21	Charge	CC	1	1 h	4.4				
		22	Rest	Open circuit		10 min					
		23	Discharge	CC	0.1	10 h	2.8				
		24	Rest	Open circuit		10 min					
		25	Charge	CC	2	30 min	4.4				
		26	Rest	Open circuit		10 min					
		27	Discharge	CC	0.1	10 h	2.8				
		28	Rest	Open circuit		10 min					
		29	Charge	CC	1	1 h	4.4				
		30	Rest	Open circuit		10 min					
		31	Discharge	CC	0.1	10 h	2.8				
		32	Rest	Open circuit		10 min					
		33	Charge	CC	0.5	2h	4.4				
		34	Rest	Open circuit		10 min					
		35	Discharge	CC	0.1	10 h	2.8				
		36	Rest	Open circuit		10 min					
		37	Charge	CC	0.2	5 h	4.4				
		38	Rest	Open circuit		10 min					
		39	Discharge	CC	0.1	10 h	2.8				
		40	Rest	Open circuit		10 min					
		41	Charge	CC	0.1	10 h	4.4				
		42	Rest	Open circuit		10 min					
		43	Discharge	CC	0.1	10 h	2.8				
		44	Rest	Open circuit		10 min					
		45	Charge	CC	0.05	20 h	4.4				
		46	Rest	Open circuit		10 min					
		47	Discharge	CC	0.1	10 h	2.8				
		48	Rest	Open circuit		10 min					
Loop	25	49	Go back to step 2 until 4								

WP2-5_I3: symmetrical rate

WP	2-5
Cell type	Li/NMC8 11
Cell format	MLPC
Protocol	WP2- 5_I3

symmetric rate: formation + initial check-up + IR + symmetric-rate test

Stage	T, oC	Step	Mode	Control	Termination conditions			Cycles	
				Current, C	Time	Voltage, V	Current		
Safety limits						<2.45, >5.1			
Pause	25	0	Rest	Open circuit		12 h			
Formation	25	1	Charge	CCCV	0.05	26 h	4.4	0.025	2
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min			
			Discharge	CC	0.05	20 h	2.8		
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min			
Check-up	25	2	Charge	CCCV	0.05	20 h	4.4	0.025	Capacity
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min			
			Discharge	CC	0.1	10 h	2.8		
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min			
Check-up	25	3	Charge	CCCV	0.05	20 h	4.4	0.025	IR
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min			
			Discharge	CC	0.1	2.5 h	25% SOD		
			Discharge	CC	0.2	30 sec			
			Rest	Open circuit		30 sec			
			Discharge	CC	0.1	2.5 h	50% SOD		
			Discharge	CC	0.2	30 sec			
			Rest	Open circuit		30 sec			
			Discharge	CC	0.1	2.5 h	75% SOD		
			Discharge	CC	0.2	30 sec			
			Rest	Open circuit		30 sec			
			Discharge	CC	0.1	2.5 h	2.8		
Rest	Open circuit		10 min						
Check-up	25	4	Charge	CC	0.05	6 h	3.85		Self discharge
			Rest	Open circuit		24 h			
			Discharge	CC	0.1	10 h	2.8		
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min			
Rate	25	5	Charge	CC	0.05	20 h	4.4		
		6	Rest	Open circuit		10 min			
		7	Discharge	CC	0.05	20 h	2.8		
		8	Rest	Open circuit		10 min			
		9	Charge	CC	0.1	10 h	4.4		

		10	Rest	Open circuit		10 min				
		11	Discharge	CC	0.1	10 h	2.8			
		12	Rest	Open circuit		10 min				
		13	Charge	CC	0.2	5 h	4.4			
		14	Rest	Open circuit		10 min				
		15	Discharge	CC	0.2	5 h	2.8			
		16	Rest	Open circuit		10 min				
		17	Charge	CC	0.5	2 h	4.4			
		18	Rest	Open circuit		10 min				
		19	Discharge	CC	0.5	2 h	2.8			
		20	Rest	Open circuit		10 min				
		21	Charge	CC	1	1 h	4.4			
		22	Rest	Open circuit		10 min				
		23	Discharge	CC	1	1 h	2.8			
		24	Rest	Open circuit		10 min				
		25	Charge	CC	2	30 min	4.4			
		26	Rest	Open circuit		10 min				
		27	Discharge	CC	2	30 min	2.8			
		28	Rest	Open circuit		10 min				
		29	Charge	CC	1	1 h	4.4			
		30	Rest	Open circuit		10 min				
		31	Discharge	CC	1	1 h	2.8			
		32	Rest	Open circuit		10 min				
		33	Charge	CC	0.5	2 h	4.4			
		34	Rest	Open circuit		10 min				
		35	Discharge	CC	0.5	2 h	2.8			
		36	Rest	Open circuit		10 min				
		37	Charge	CC	0.2	5 h	4.4			
		38	Rest	Open circuit		10 min				
		39	Discharge	CC	0.2	5 h	2.8			
		40	Rest	Open circuit		10 min				
		41	Charge	CC	0.1	10 h	4.4			
		42	Rest	Open circuit		10 min				
		43	Discharge	CC	0.1	10 h	2.8			
		44	Rest	Open circuit		10 min				
		45	Charge	CC	0.05	20 h	4.4			
		46	Rest	Open circuit		10 min				
		47	Discharge	CC	0.05	20 h	2.8			
		48	Rest	Open circuit		10 min				
Loop	25	49	Go back to step 2 until 4							

WP2-5_I4: calendar ageing

Cell format	MLPC
Protocol	WP2-5_I4

Calendar Ageing - initial check-up + calendar ageing test

Stage	T, °C	Step	Mode	Control conditions			Termination conditions			Cycles
				Time	Voltage, V	Current, C	Time	Voltage, V	Current	
Safety limits								<2.45, >4.5		
Pause	25	0	Rest	Open circuit			12 h			
Check-up	25	1	Charge	CCCV		0.33		Vmax	0.020	Capacity
			Rest	Open circuit			10 min			
			Discharge	CC		0.33		Vmin		
			Rest	Open circuit			10 min			
Calendar ageing	25	2	Charge	CC		0.33		V max		Ageing
			Rest	Open circuit			10 h			
	45	Rest	thermalization			3h				
		Rest	ageing							
		Rest	Open circuit			7 days				
Loop 1	25	3	Go back to step 0							

WP3-5_L1: standard cycling protocols for BEV

Cell format	MLPC
Protocol	WP3-5_L1

Long-term cycling- Standard - initial check-up + check-up cycle and IR check

Stage	T, °C	Step	Mode	Control conditions			Termination conditions			Cycles
				Time	Voltage, V	Current, C	Time	Voltage, V	Current	
Safety limits								<2.45, >4.5		
Pause	25	0	Rest	Open circuit			12 h			
Check-up	25	1	Charge	CCCV		0.33		Vmax	0.020	Capacity
			Rest	Open circuit			10 min			
			Discharge	CC		0.33		Vmin		
			Rest	Open circuit			10 min			
Check-up	25	2	Charge	CCCV		0.33		V max	0.020	IR
			Rest	Open circuit			10 min			
			Discharge	CC		0.1		20% SOD		
			Rest	Open circuit			10 min			
			Discharge	CC		1	10 sec			
			Rest	Open circuit			10 min			
			Charge	CC		1	10 sec			
			Rest	Open circuit			10 min			
			Discharge	CC		0.1		50% SOD		
			Rest	Open circuit			10 min			

			Discharge	CC			1	10 sec			
			Rest	Open circuit				10 min			
			Charge	CC			1	10 sec			
			Rest	Open circuit				10 min			
			Discharge	CC			0.1		80% SOD		
			Rest	Open circuit				10 min			
			Discharge	CC			1	10 sec			
			Rest	Open circuit				10 min			
			Charge	CC			1	10 sec			
			Rest	Open circuit				10 min			
			Discharge	CC			0.1		V min		
			Rest	Open circuit				10 min			
Cycle ageing	25	3	Charge	CCCV			0.33		Vmax	0.020	Ageing
			Rest	Open circuit				10 min			
			Discharge	CC			0.33		V min		
			Rest	Open circuit				10 min			
Loop 1	25	4	Go back to step 1 & skip step 2 each 10 cycles								
Loop 2	25	5	Go back to step 1+2 each 50 cycles								

WP3-5_L2: drive protocols for BEV

Cell format	MLPC
Protocol	WP3-5_L2

Long-term cycling - Drive Profile - initial check-up + check-up cycle and IR check

Stage	T, °C	Step	Mode	Control conditions			Termination conditions			Cycle s
				Time	Voltage, V	Current, C	Time	Voltage, V	Current	
Safety limits								<2.45, >4.5		
Pause	25	0	Rest	Open circuit			12 h			
Check-up	25	1	Charge	CCCV		0.33		Vmax	0.020	Capacity
			Rest	Open circuit			10 min			
			Discharge	CC		0.33		Vmin		
			Rest	Open circuit			10 min			
Check-up	25	2	Charge	CCCV		0.33		V max	0.020	IR
			Rest	Open circuit			10 min			
			Discharge	CC		0.1		20% SOD		
			Rest	Open circuit			10 min			
			Discharge	CC		1	10 sec			
			Rest	Open circuit			10 min			
Charge	CC			1	10 sec					

			Rest	Open circuit				10 min				
			Discharge	CC			0.1		50% SOD			
			Rest	Open circuit				10 min				
			Discharge	CC			1	10 sec				
			Rest	Open circuit				10 min				
			Charge	CC			1	10 sec				
			Rest	Open circuit				10 min				
			Discharge	CC			0.1		80% SOD			
			Rest	Open circuit				10 min				
			Discharge	CC			1	10 sec				
			Rest	Open circuit				10 min				
			Charge	CC			1	10 sec				
			Rest	Open circuit				10 min				
			Discharge	CC			0.1		V min			
			Rest	Open circuit				10 min				
Cycle ageing	25	3	Charge	CCCV			0.33		VmaxOP	0.020	Ageing	
			Rest	Open circuit					10 min			
			Discharge	WLTP			W profile			V mix OP		
			Rest	Open circuit					10 min			
Loop 1	25	4	Go back to step 1 & skip step 2 each 10 cycles									
Loop 2	25	5	Go back to step 1+2 each 50 cycles									

Vmax OP	95% SoC
VminOP	5% SoC

WP3-5_L3: fast charge protocols for BEV

Cell format	MLPC
Protocol	WP3-5_L3

Long-term cycling - Fast Charge - initial check-up + check-up cycle and IR check

Stage	T, °C	Step	Mode	Control conditions			Termination conditions			Cycles
				Time	Voltage, V	Current, C	Time	Voltage, V	Current	
Safety limits								<2.45, >4.5		
Pause	25	0	Rest	Open circuit			12 h			
Check-up	25	1	Charge	CCCV		0.33		Vmax	0.020	Capacity
			Rest	Open circuit			10 min			
			Discharge	CC		0.33		Vmin		
			Rest	Open circuit			10 min			
	25	2	Charge	CCCV		0.33		V max	0.020	IR

Check-up			Rest	Open circuit				10 min				
			Discharge	CC			0.1			20% SOD		
			Rest	Open circuit						10 min		
			Discharge	CC			1		10 sec			
			Rest	Open circuit						10 min		
			Charge	CC			1		10 sec			
			Rest	Open circuit						10 min		
			Discharge	CC			0.1				50% SOD	
			Rest	Open circuit						10 min		
			Discharge	CC			1		10 sec			
			Rest	Open circuit						10 min		
			Charge	CC			1		10 sec			
			Rest	Open circuit						10 min		
			Discharge	CC			0.1					80% SOD
			Rest	Open circuit						10 min		
			Discharge	CC			1		10 sec			
			Rest	Open circuit						10 min		
			Charge	CC			1		10 sec			
			Rest	Open circuit						10 min		
			Discharge	CC			0.1					V min
Rest	Open circuit						10 min					
Cycle ageing	25	3	Charge	CC			0.33		VminDoD		VmaxDoD	
			Charge	CC			TBD		VmaxDoD		80% SoC	
			Rest	Open circuit					10 min			
			Discharge	CC			0.33			VminDoD		VminDoD
			Rest	Open circuit						10 min		20% SoC
Ageing												
Loop 1	25	4	Go back to step 1 & skip step 2 each 10 cycles									
Loop 2	25	5	Go back to step 1+2 each 50 cycles									

WP3-5_L4: C-rate and light profile (school laps) aging test for EVTOL

Cell format	MLPC
Protocol	WP3-5_L4

Battery rated capacity + flight profile (school laps) aging test

Stage	T, °C	Step	Mode	Control conditions			Termination conditions			Cycles
				Time	Voltage, V	Current, C	Time	Voltage, V	Current	
Safety limits								<2.45, >4.5		

Reset	23	0	Rest	Open circuit				10 min			
Check-up	23	1	Charge	CCCV			0.33		Vmax	0.020	Capacity
			Rest	Open circuit				10 min			
			Discharge	CC			1		Vmin		
			Rest	Open circuit				10 min			
Cycle ageing	TCP-02	2	Charge	CCP-01		Confidential					Ageing
			Rest	Open circuit				10 min			
			Discharge	DGP-01		Confidential					
			Rest	Open circuit				10 min			
Loop 1		3	Go back to step 1+2 each 50 cycles and measure internal resistance in accordance to ATP until 0% SOH								

WP3-5_L5: cycling protocol for high-rate battery for EVTOL

Cell format	MLPC
Protocol	WP3-5_L5

Cycle test for high rate battery

Stage	T, °C	Step	Mode	Control conditions			Termination conditions			Cycles	
				Time	Voltage, V	Current, C	Time	Voltage, V	Current		
Safety limits								<2.45, >4.5			
Reset	23	0	Rest	Open circuit			10 min				
Check-up 1	23	1	Charge	CCCV		0.33		Vmax	0.020	Capacity	
			Rest	Open circuit			10 min				
			Discharge	CC		1		Vmin			
			Rest	Open circuit			10 min				
Charge		2	Charge	CCCV		0.33		Vmax	0.020		
			Rest	Open circuit			10 min				
Cycle ageing	23	3	Discharge	CC		10		80% SOC		Ageing	
			Rest	Open circuit			10 min				
			Charge	CCCV		5 - 10		Vmax	0.020		
			Rest	Open circuit			< 2 hours				
Loop 1		4	Go back to step 3 each 100 cycles unless otherwise specified in the design documentation. If the battery charging or discharging is inhibited due to thermal constraints, the battery shall be allowed to cool enough to allow continued cycling. Temperature measurement is required during the cycling near terminals.								
Check-up 2	23	5	Discharge	CC		1		Vmin		Capacity 2	
Check-up 1	23	6	Charge	CCCV		0.33		Vmax	0.020	Capacity	
			Rest	Open circuit			10 min				

		Discharge	CC			1		V _{min}	
		Rest	Open circuit				10 min		

3.7. TESTING PROTOCOLS FOR LCC/NMC CELLS

- Lithiophilic current collector – solid electrolyte separator – NMC cathode (LCC/NMC)

WP2_F2: long-term cycling 100% DOD Coin cell

WP	2
Cell type	Li/NMC811
Cell format	Coin cells
Protocol	WP2_F2

Stage	T, °C	Step	Mode	Control conditions			Termination conditions			Cycles
				Time	Voltage, V	Current, C	Time	Voltage, V	Current	
Safety limits								<2.45, >4.9		
Pause	25	0	Rest	Open circuit			12 h			
Formation cycle	25	1	Charge	CCCV		0.05	26 h	4.8	0.025	1
			Rest	Open circuit			10 min			
			Discharge	CC		0.05	20h	2.8		
			Rest	Open circuit			10 min			
Galvanostatic cycling	25	2	Charge	CCCV		0.05	26 h	4.6	0.025	3000
			Rest	Open circuit			10 min			
			Discharge	CC		0.1		2.8		
			Rest	Open circuit			10 min			

WP3-5_H4: long-term cycling 100% DOD

WP	WP3-5
Cell type	Li/NMC811
Cell format	MLPC
Protocol	WP3-5_H4

Standard cycling protocol

Long-term cycling 100% DOD - Till CR<75% + formation + initial check-up + check-up cycle and IR check

Stage	T, °C	Step	Mode	Control	Termination conditions			Cycles	
				Current, C	Time	Voltage, V	Current		
Safety limits						<2.45, >4.9			
Pause	25	0	Rest	Open circuit		12 h			
Formation	25	1	Charge	CCCV	0.05	26 h	4.8	0.025	1
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min			
			Discharge	CC	0.05	20 h	2.8		
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min			

Formation	25	2	Charge	CCCV	0.05	26 h	4.6	0.025	1
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min			
			Discharge	CC	0.05	20 h	2.8		
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min			
Check-up	25	3	Charge	CCCV	0.05	20 h	4.6	0.025	Capacity
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min			
			Discharge	CC	0.1	10 h	2.8		
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min			
Check-up	25	4	Charge	CCCV	0.05	20 h	4.6	0.025	IR
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min			
			Discharge	CC	0.1	2.5 h	25% SOD		
			Discharge	CC	0.2	30 sec			
			Rest	Open circuit		30 sec			
			Discharge	CC	0.1	2.5 h	50% SOD		
			Discharge	CC	0.2	30 sec			
			Rest	Open circuit		30 sec			
			Discharge	CC	0.1	2.5 h	75% SOD		
			Discharge	CC	0.2	30 sec			
			Rest	Open circuit		30 sec			
			Discharge	CC	0.1	2.5 h	2.8		
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min			
			Check-up	25	5	Charge	CC	0.05	
Rest	Open circuit					24 h			
Discharge	CC	0.1				10 h	2.8		
Rest	Open circuit					10 min			
Cycling 100% DOD	25	6	Charge	CCCV	0.05	20 h	4.6	0.025	50
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min			
			Discharge	CC	0.1	10 h	2.8		
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min			
Loop	25	7	Go back to step 2 each 50 cycles						

WP3-5_H5: long term cycling 80% DOD

WP	WP3-5	Standard cycling protocol
Cell type	LCC/ NMC8 11	
Cell format	MLPC	
Protocol	WP3-5 H5	

**Long-term cycling 80% DOD (100%-20% SOC)-
Till CR<75% + formation + initial check-up +
check-up cycle and IR check**

Stage	T, °C	Step	Mode	Control	Termination conditions			Cycles
				Current, C	Time	Voltage, V	Current	
Safety limits						<2.45, >4.9		

Pause	25	0	Rest	Open circuit		12 h				
Formation	25	1	Charge	CCCV	0.05	26 h	4.8	0.025	1	
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min				
			Discharge	CC	0.05	20 h	2.8			
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min				
Formation	25	1	Charge	CCCV	0.05	26 h	4.6	0.025	1	
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min				
			Discharge	CC	0.05	20 h	2.8			
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min				
Check-up	25	2	Charge	CCCV	0.05	20 h	4.6	0.025	Capacity	
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min				
			Discharge	CC	0.1	10 h	2.8			
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min				
Check-up	25	3	Charge	CCCV	0.05	20 h	4.6	0.025	IR	
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min				
			Discharge	CC	0.1	2.5 h	25% SOD			
			Discharge	CC	0.2	30 sec				
			Rest	Open circuit		30 sec				
			Discharge	CC	0.1	2.5 h	50% SOD			
			Discharge	CC	0.2	30 sec				
			Rest	Open circuit		30 sec				
			Discharge	CC	0.1	2.5 h	75% SOD			
			Discharge	CC	0.2	30 sec				
			Rest	Open circuit		30 sec				
			Discharge	CC	0.1	2.5 h	2.8			
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min				
			Check-up	25	4	Charge	CC	0.05		6 h
Rest	Open circuit					24 h				
Discharge	CC	0.1				10 h	2.8			
Rest	Open circuit					10 min				
Cycling 80% DOD	25	5	Charge	CCCV	0.05	20 h	4.6	0.025	50	
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min				
			Discharge	CC	0.1	10 h	3.8			
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min				
Loop	25	6	Go back to step 2 each 50 cycles							

WP3-5_H6: long term cycling 50% DOD

WP	WP3-5
Cell type	LCC/ NMC8 11
Cell format	MLPC
Protocol	WP3- 5_ H6

Standard cycling protocol

Long-term cycling 50% DOD (70%-20% SOC) - Till CR<75% + formation + initial check-up + check-up cycle and IR check

Stage	T, oC	Step		Mode	Control			Termination conditions Current	
					Current, C	Time	Voltage, V		
Safety limits						<2.45, >4.9			
Pause	25	0	Rest	Open circuit		12 h			
Formation	25	1	Charge	CCCV	0.05	26 h	4.8	0.025	1
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min			
			Discharge	CC	0.05	20 h	2.8		
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min			
Formation	25	1	Charge	CCCV	0.05	26 h	4.6	0.025	1
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min			
			Discharge	CC	0.05	20 h	2.8		
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min			
Check-up	25	2	Charge	CCCV	0.05	20 h	4.6	0.025	Capacity
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min			
			Discharge	CC	0.1	10 h	2.8		
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min			
Check-up	25	3	Charge	CCCV	0.05	20 h	4.6	0.025	IR
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min			
			Discharge	CC	0.1	2.5 h	25% SOD		
			Discharge	CC	0.2	30 sec			
			Rest	Open circuit		30 sec			
			Discharge	CC	0.1	2.5 h	50% SOD		
			Discharge	CC	0.2	30 sec			
			Rest	Open circuit		30 sec			
			Discharge	CC	0.1	2.5 h	75% SOD		
			Discharge	CC	0.2	30 sec			
			Rest	Open circuit		30 sec			
			Discharge	CC	0.1	2.5 h	2.8		
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min			
			Check-up	25	4	Charge	CC	0.05	
Rest	Open circuit					24 h			
Discharge	CC	0.1				10 h	2.8		
Rest	Open circuit					10 min			
	25	5	Charge	CCCV	0.05	20 h	4.3	0.025	50

Cycling 50% DOD			Rest	Open circuit		10 min		
			Discharge	CC	0.1	10 h	3.8	
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min		
Loop	25	6	Go back to step 2 each 50 cycles					

WP2-5_H7: D-rate

WP	2-5
Cell type	LCC/NM C811
Cell format	MLPC
Protocol	WP2- 5_H7

**D rate: formation + initial check-up + IR
+ D-rate test**

Stage	T, °C	Step	Mode	Control	Termination conditions			Cycles	
				Current, C	Time	Voltage, V	Current		
Safety limits						<2.45, >5.1			
Pause	25	0	Rest	Open circuit		12 h			
Formation	25	1	Charge	CCCV	0.05	26 h	4.8	0.025	2
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min			
			Discharge	CC	0.05	20 h	2.8		
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min			
Check-up	25	2	Charge	CCCV	0.05	20 h	4.6	0.025	Capacity
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min			
			Discharge	CC	0.1	10 h	2.8		
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min			
Check-up	25	3	Charge	CCCV	0.05	20 h	4.6	0.025	IR
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min			
			Discharge	CC	0.1	2.5 h	25% SOD		
			Discharge	CC	0.2	30 sec			
			Rest	Open circuit		30 sec			
			Discharge	CC	0.1	2.5 h	50% SOD		
			Discharge	CC	0.2	30 sec			
			Rest	Open circuit		30 sec			
			Discharge	CC	0.1	2.5 h	75% SOD		
			Discharge	CC	0.2	30 sec			
			Rest	Open circuit		30 sec			
			Discharge	CC	0.1	2.5 h	2.8		
Check-up	25	4	Charge	CC	0.05	6 h	3.9		Self discharge
			Rest	Open circuit		24 h			
			Discharge	CC	0.1	10 h	2.8		
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min			

D-Rate	25	5	Charge	CCCV	0.05	26 h	4.6	0.025		
		6	Rest	Open circuit		10 min				
		7	Discharge	CC	0.1	10 h	2.8			
		8	Rest	Open circuit		10 min				
		9	Charge	CCCV	0.05	26 h	4.6	0.025		
		10	Rest	Open circuit		10 min				
		11	Discharge	CC	0.2	5 h	2.8			
		12	Rest	Open circuit		10 min				
		13	Charge	CCCV	0.05	26 h	4.6	0.025		
		14	Rest	Open circuit		10 min				
		15	Discharge	CC	0.5	2 h	2.8			
		16	Rest	Open circuit		10 min				
		17	Charge	CCCV	0.05	26 h	4.6	0.025		
		18	Rest	Open circuit		10 min				
		19	Discharge	CC	1	1 h	2.8			
		20	Rest	Open circuit		10 min				
		21	Charge	CCCV	0.05	26 h	4.6	0.025		
		22	Rest	Open circuit		10 min				
		23	Discharge	CC	2	30 min	2.8			
		24	Rest	Open circuit		10 min				
		25	Charge	CCCV	0.05	26 h	4.6	0.025		
		26	Rest	Open circuit		10 min				
		27	Discharge	CC	1	1 h	2.8			
		28	Rest	Open circuit		10 min				
		29	Charge	CCCV	0.05	26 h	4.6	0.025		
		30	Rest	Open circuit		10 min				
		31	Discharge	CC	0.5	2 h	2.8			
		32	Rest	Open circuit		10 min				
		33	Charge	CCCV	0.05	26 h	4.6	0.025		
		34	Rest	Open circuit		10 min				
		35	Discharge	CC	0.2	5 h	2.8			
		36	Rest	Open circuit		10 min				
		37	Charge	CCCV	0.05	26 h	4.6	0.025		
		38	Rest	Open circuit		10 min				
		39	Discharge	CC	0.1	10 h	2.8			
		40	Rest	Open circuit		10 min				
		Loop	25	41	Go back to step 2 until 4					

WP2-5_H8: C-rate

WP	2-5
Cell type	LCC/NMC81 1
Cell format	MLPC
Protocol	WP2-5_H8

C rate: formation + initial check-up + IR + C-rate test

Stage	T, °C	Step	Mode	Control	Termination conditions			Cycles	
				Current, C	Time	Voltage, V	Current		
Safety limits						<2.45, >5.1			
Pause	25	0	Rest	Open circuit		12 h			
Formation	25	1	Charge	CCCV	0.05	26 h	4.8	0.025	2
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min			
			Discharge	CC	0.05	20 h	2.8		
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min			
Check-up	25	2	Charge	CCCV	0.05	20 h	4.6	0.025	Capacity
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min			
			Discharge	CC	0.1	10 h	2.8		
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min			
Check-up	25	3	Charge	CCCV	0.05	20 h	4.6	0.025	IR
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min			
			Discharge	CC	0.1	2.5 h	25% SOD		
			Discharge	CC	0.2	30 sec			
			Rest	Open circuit		30 sec			
			Discharge	CC	0.1	2.5 h	50% SOD		
			Discharge	CC	0.2	30 sec			
			Rest	Open circuit		30 sec			
			Discharge	CC	0.1	2.5 h	75% SOD		
			Discharge	CC	0.2	30 sec			
			Rest	Open circuit		30 sec			
			Discharge	CC	0.1	2.5 h	2.8		
Check-up	25	4	Charge	CC	0.05	6 h	3.9		Self discharge
			Rest	Open circuit		24 h			
			Discharge	CC	0.1	10 h	2.8		
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min			
C-Rate	25	5	Charge	CC	0.05	20 h	4.6		
		6	Rest	Open circuit		10 min			
		7	Discharge	CC	0.1	10 h	2.8		

8	Rest	Open circuit		10 min			
9	Charge	CC	0.1	10 h	4.6		
10	Rest	Open circuit		10 min			
11	Discharge	CC	0.1	10 h	2.8		
12	Rest	Open circuit		10 min			
13	Charge	CC	0.2	5 h	4.6		
14	Rest	Open circuit		10 min			
15	Discharge	CC	0.1	10 h	2.8		
16	Rest	Open circuit		10 min			
17	Charge	CC	0.5	2 h	4.6		
18	Rest	Open circuit		10 min			
19	Discharge	CC	0.1	10 h	2.8		
20	Rest	Open circuit		10 min			
21	Charge	CC	1	1 h	4.6		
22	Rest	Open circuit		10 min			
23	Discharge	CC	0.1	10 h	2.8		
24	Rest	Open circuit		10 min			
25	Charge	CC	2	30 min	4.6		
26	Rest	Open circuit		10 min			
27	Discharge	CC	0.1	10 h	2.8		
28	Rest	Open circuit		10 min			
29	Charge	CC	1	1 h	4.6		
30	Rest	Open circuit		10 min			
31	Discharge	CC	0.1	10 h	2.8		
32	Rest	Open circuit		10 min			
33	Charge	CC	0.5	2h	4.6		
34	Rest	Open circuit		10 min			
35	Discharge	CC	0.1	10 h	2.8		
36	Rest	Open circuit		10 min			
37	Charge	CC	0.2	5 h	4.6		
38	Rest	Open circuit		10 min			
39	Discharge	CC	0.1	10 h	2.8		
40	Rest	Open circuit		10 min			
41	Charge	CC	0.1	10 h	4.6		
42	Rest	Open circuit		10 min			
43	Discharge	CC	0.1	10 h	2.8		

		4	Rest	Open circuit		10 min		
		4	Charge	CC	0.05	20 h	4.6	
		4	Rest	Open circuit		10 min		
		4	Discharge	CC	0.1	10 h	2.8	
		4	Rest	Open circuit		10 min		
Loop	25	4	Go back to step 2 until 4					

WP2-5_H9: symmetrical rate

WP	2-5
Cell type	LCC/NM C811
Cell format	MLPC
Protocol	WP2- 5_H9

symmetric rate: formation + initial check-up + IR + symmetric-rate test

Stage	T, °C	Step	Mode	Control	Termination conditions			Cycles	
				Current, C	Time	Voltage, V	Current		
Safety limits						<2.45, >5.1			
Pause	25	0	Rest	Open circuit		12 h			
Formation	25	1	Charge	CCCV	0.05	26 h	4.8	0.025	2
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min			
			Discharge	CC	0.05	20 h	2.8		
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min			
Check-up	25	2	Charge	CCCV	0.05	20 h	4.6	0.025	Capacity
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min			
			Discharge	CC	0.1	10 h	2.8		
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min			
Check-up	25	3	Charge	CCCV	0.05	20 h	4.6	0.025	IR
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min			
			Discharge	CC	0.1	2.5 h	25% SOD		
			Discharge	CC	0.2	30 sec			
			Rest	Open circuit		30 sec			
			Discharge	CC	0.1	2.5 h	50% SOD		
			Discharge	CC	0.2	30 sec			
			Rest	Open circuit		30 sec			
			Discharge	CC	0.1	2.5 h	75% SOD		
			Discharge	CC	0.2	30 sec			
			Rest	Open circuit		30 sec			
			Discharge	CC	0.1	2.5 h	2.8		
Rest	Open circuit		10 min						
Check-up	25	4	Charge	CC	0.05	6 h	3.9		

			Rest	Open circuit		24 h		Self discharge
			Discharge	CC	0.1	10 h	2.8	
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min		
Rate	25	5	Charge	CC	0.05	20 h	4.6	
		6	Rest	Open circuit		10 min		
		7	Discharge	CC	0.05	20 h	2.8	
		8	Rest	Open circuit		10 min		
		9	Charge	CC	0.1	10 h	4.6	
		10	Rest	Open circuit		10 min		
		11	Discharge	CC	0.1	10 h	2.8	
		12	Rest	Open circuit		10 min		
		13	Charge	CC	0.2	5 h	4.6	
		14	Rest	Open circuit		10 min		
		15	Discharge	CC	0.2	5 h	2.8	
		16	Rest	Open circuit		10 min		
		17	Charge	CC	0.5	2 h	4.6	
		18	Rest	Open circuit		10 min		
		19	Discharge	CC	0.5	2 h	2.8	
		20	Rest	Open circuit		10 min		
		21	Charge	CC	1	1 h	4.6	
		22	Rest	Open circuit		10 min		
		23	Discharge	CC	1	1 h	2.8	
		24	Rest	Open circuit		10 min		
		25	Charge	CC	2	30 min	4.6	
		26	Rest	Open circuit		10 min		
		27	Discharge	CC	2	30 min	2.8	
		28	Rest	Open circuit		10 min		
		29	Charge	CC	1	1 h	4.6	
		30	Rest	Open circuit		10 min		
		31	Discharge	CC	1	1 h	2.8	
		32	Rest	Open circuit		10 min		
		33	Charge	CC	0.5	2 h	4.6	
		34	Rest	Open circuit		10 min		
		35	Discharge	CC	0.5	2 h	2.8	
		36	Rest	Open circuit		10 min		
		37	Charge	CC	0.2	5 h	4.6	
		38	Rest	Open circuit		10 min		
		39	Discharge	CC	0.2	5 h	2.8	
		40	Rest	Open circuit		10 min		
		41	Charge	CC	0.1	10 h	4.6	
		42	Rest	Open circuit		10 min		

		43	Discharge	CC	0.1	10 h	2.8		
		44	Rest	Open circuit		10 min			
		45	Charge	CC	0.05	20 h	4.6		
		46	Rest	Open circuit		10 min			
		47	Discharge	CC	0.05	20 h	2.8		
		48	Rest	Open circuit		10 min			
Loop	25	49	Go back to step 2 until 4						

3.8. ABUSE TESTING

- General formation protocols for cell delivery for Li/NMC cells

WP5_M1: formation protocol for Li/NMC cells

WP	WP5
Cell type	Li/NMC811
Cell format	MLPC
Protocol	WP5_M1

Formation up to 30% SOC for cell delivery

Stage	T, °C	Step	Mode	Control	Termination conditions			Cycles	
				Current, C	Time	Voltage, V	Current		
Safety limits						<2.45, >4.5			
Pause	25	0	Rest	Open circuit		12 h			
Formation	25	1	Charge	CCCV	0.05	26 h	4.4	0.025	2
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min			
			Discharge	CC	0.05	20 h	2.8		
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min			
Check-up	25	2	Charge	CCCV	0.05	20 h	4.4	0.025	Capacity
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min			
			Discharge	CC	0.1	10 h	2.8		
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min			
Check-up	25	3	Charge	CCCV	0.05	20 h	4.4	0.025	IR
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min			
			Discharge	CC	0.1	2.5 h	25% SOD		
			Discharge	CC	0.2	30 sec			
			Rest	Open circuit		30 sec			
			Discharge	CC	0.1	2.5 h	50% SOD		
			Discharge	CC	0.2	30 sec			
			Rest	Open circuit		30 sec			
Discharge	CC	0.1	2.5 h	75% SOD					

			Discharge	CC	0.2	30 sec			
			Rest	Open circuit		30 sec			
			Discharge	CC	0.1	2.5 h	2.8		
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min			
Check-up	25	4	Charge	CC	0.05	6 h	3.85		Self discharge
			Rest	Open circuit		24 h			
			Discharge	CC	0.1	10 h	2.8		
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min			
Charge 30% SOC	25	5	Charge	CCCV	0.05	6 h	3.85	0.025	
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min			

- General charging protocol up to 100% SOC after Li/NMC cells are received

WP5_M2: charging protocol from 30% to 100% SOC for Li/NMC cells

WP	WP5
Cell type	Li/NMC811
Cell format	MLPC
Protocol	WP5_M2

Charge from 30% to 100 % SOC

Stage	T, °C	Step	Mode	Control	Termination conditions			Cycles	
				Current, C	Time	Voltage, V	Current		
Safety limits						<2.45, >4.5			
Pause	25	0	Rest	Open circuit		12 h			
Residual charge	25	1	Charge	CCCV	0.05	16 h	4.4	0.025	2
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min			
			Discharge	CC	0.05	20 h	2.8		
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min			
Check-up	25	2	Charge	CCCV	0.05	20 h	4.4	0.025	Capacity
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min			
			Discharge	CC	0.1	10 h	2.8		
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min			
Check-up	25	3	Charge	CCCV	0.05	20 h	4.4	0.025	IR
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min			
			Discharge	CC	0.1	2.5 h	25% SOD		
			Discharge	CC	0.2	30 sec			
			Rest	Open circuit		30 sec			
			Discharge	CC	0.1	2.5 h	50% SOD		
			Discharge	CC	0.2	30 sec			
			Rest	Open circuit		30 sec			
			Discharge	CC	0.1	2.5 h	75% SOD		
Discharge	CC	0.2	30 sec						

			Rest	Open circuit		30 sec			
			Discharge	CC	0.1	2.5 h	2.8		
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min			
Charge 100% SOC	25	5	Charge	CCCV	0.05	20 h	4.4	0.025	
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min			

- **General formation protocol for cell delivery of LCC/NMC cells**

WP5_M3: formation protocol for LCC/NMC cells

WP	WP5
Cell type	LCC/ NMC811
Cell format	MLPC
Protocol	WP5_M3

Formation up to 30% SOC for cell delivery

Stage	T, °C	Step	Mode	Control	Termination conditions			Cycles	
				Current, C	Time	Voltage, V	Current		
Safety limits						<2.45, >4.9			
Pause	25	0	Rest	Open circuit		12 h			
Formation	25	1	Charge	CCCV	0.05	26 h	4.8	0.025	2
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min			
			Discharge	CC	0.05	20 h	2.8		
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min			
Check-up	25	2	Charge	CCCV	0.05	20 h	4.6	0.025	Capacity
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min			
			Discharge	CC	0.1	10 h	2.8		
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min			
Check-up	25	3	Charge	CCCV	0.05	20 h	4.6	0.025	IR
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min			
			Discharge	CC	0.1	2.5 h	25% SOD		
			Discharge	CC	0.2	30 sec			
			Rest	Open circuit		30 sec			
			Discharge	CC	0.1	2.5 h	50% SOD		
			Discharge	CC	0.2	30 sec			
			Rest	Open circuit		30 sec			
			Discharge	CC	0.1	2.5 h	75% SOD		
			Discharge	CC	0.2	30 sec			
			Rest	Open circuit		30 sec			
			Discharge	CC	0.1	2.5 h	2.8		
Rest	Open circuit		10 min						
Check-up	25	4	Charge	CC	0.05	6 h	3.9		

			Rest	Open circuit		24 h			Self discharge
			Discharge	CC	0.1	10 h	2.8		
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min			
Charge 30% SOC	25	5	Charge	CCCV	0.05	6 h	3.9	0.025	
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min			

WP5_M4: general charging protocol up to 100% SOC after LCC/NMC cells received

WP	WP5
Cell type	LCC/NMC811
Cell format	MLPC
Protocol	WP5_M4

Charge from 30% to 100 % SOC

Stage	T, °C	Step	Mode	Control	Termination conditions			Cycles	
				Current, C	Time	Voltage, V	Current		
Safety limits						<2.45, >4.9			
Pause	25	0	Rest	Open circuit		12 h			
Residual charge	25	1	Charge	CCCV	0.05	16 h	4.8	0.025	2
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min			
			Discharge	CC	0.05	20 h	2.8		
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min			
Check-up	25	2	Charge	CCCV	0.05	20 h	4.6	0.025	Capacity
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min			
			Discharge	CC	0.1	10 h	2.8		
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min			
Check-up	25	3	Charge	CCCV	0.05	20 h	4.6	0.025	IR
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min			
			Discharge	CC	0.1	2.5 h	25% SOD		
			Discharge	CC	0.2	30 sec			
			Rest	Open circuit		30 sec			
			Discharge	CC	0.1	2.5 h	50% SOD		
			Discharge	CC	0.2	30 sec			
			Rest	Open circuit		30 sec			
			Discharge	CC	0.1	2.5 h	75% SOD		
			Discharge	CC	0.2	30 sec			
			Rest	Open circuit		30 sec			
			Discharge	CC	0.1	2.5 h	2.8		
Charge 100% SOC	25	5	Charge	CCCV	0.05	20 h	4.6	0.025	
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min			

3.9. TESTING PROTOCOLS FOR SAFETY ASSESSMENT

- General formation protocol for Li/NMC811 cell delivery at 30% SOC

WP5_M1: formation protocol for Li/NMC811 cells

WP	WP5
Cell type	Li/NMC811
Cell format	MLPC
Protocol	WP5_M1

Formation up to 30% SOC for cell delivery

Stage	T, °C	Step	Mode	Control	Termination conditions				Cycles	
				Current, C	Time	Voltage, V	Current	Capacity		
Safety limits						<2.45, >4.5				
Pause	25	0	Rest	Open circuit		12 h				
Formation	25	1	Charge	CCCV	0.05	26 h	4.4	0.025	2	
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min				
			Discharge	CC	0.05	20 h	2.8			
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min				
Check-up	25	2	Charge	CCCV	0.05	20 h	4.4	0.025	Capacity	
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min				
			Discharge	CC	0.1	10 h	2.8			Register capacity
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min				
Check-up	25	3	Charge	CCCV	0.05	20 h	4.4	0.025	IR	
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min				
			Discharge	CC	0.1	2.5 h	25% SOD			
			Discharge	CC	0.2	30 sec				
			Rest	Open circuit		30 sec				
			Discharge	CC	0.1	2.5 h	50% SOD			
			Discharge	CC	0.2	30 sec				
			Rest	Open circuit		30 sec				
			Discharge	CC	0.1	2.5 h	75% SOD			
			Discharge	CC	0.2	30 sec				
			Rest	Open circuit		30 sec				
			Discharge	CC	0.1	2.5 h	2.8			

			Rest	Open circuit		10 min				
Check-up	25	4	Charge	CC	0.05	6 h	3.85		Self discharge	
			Rest	Open circuit		24 h				
			Discharge	CC	0.1	10 h	2.8			
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min				
Charge 30% SOC	25	5	Charge	CCCV	0.05	6 h		0.025	SOC30 – cap check	
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min				

- General charging protocol up to 100% SOC after Li/NMC811 cells received

WP5_M2: charging protocol from 30% to 100% SOC for Li/NMC811 cells

WP	WP5
Cell type	Li/NMC811
Cell format	MLPC
Protocol	WP5_M2

Charge from 30% to 100 % SOC

Stage	T, °C	Step	Mode	Control	Termination conditions			Cycles		
				Current, C	Time	Voltage, V	Current			
Safety limits						<2.45, >4.5				
Pause	25	0	Rest	Open circuit		12 h				
Residual charge	25	1	Charge	CCCV	0.05	16 h	4.4	0.025	2	
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min				
			Discharge	CC	0.05	20 h	2.8			
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min				
Check-up	25	2	Charge	CCCV	0.05	20 h	4.4	0.025	Capacity	
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min				
			Discharge	CC	0.1	10 h	2.8			
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min				
Check-up	25	3	Charge	CCCV	0.05	20 h	4.4	0.025	IR	
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min				
			Discharge	CC	0.1	2.5 h	25% SOD			
			Discharge	CC	0.2	30 sec				
			Rest	Open circuit		30 sec				
			Discharge	CC	0.1	2.5 h	50% SOD			
			Discharge	CC	0.2	30 sec				
			Rest	Open circuit		30 sec				
			Discharge	CC	0.1	2.5 h	75% SOD			
			Discharge	CC	0.2	30 sec				

			Rest	Open circuit		30 sec			
			Discharge	CC	0.1	2.5 h	2.8		
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min			
Charge 100% SOC	25	5	Charge	CCCV	0.05	20 h	4.4	0.025	
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min			

- **General formation protocol for cell delivery of LCC/Li-rich NMC cells**

WP5_M3: charging protocol upto 30% SOC for LCC/NMC811 cells

WP	WP5	
Cell type	LCC/ NMC81 1	
Cell format	MLPC	
Protocol	WP5_M 3	Formation up to 30% SOC for cell delivery

Stage	T, °C	Step	Mode	Control	Termination conditions			Capacity	Cycles	
				Current, C	Time	Voltage, V	Current			
Safety limits						<2.45, >4.9				
Pause	25	0	Rest	Open circuit		12 h				
Formation	25	1	Charge	CCCV	0.05	26 h	4.8	0.025	2	
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min				
			Discharge	CC	0.05	20 h	2.8			
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min				
Check-up	25	2	Charge	CCCV	0.05	20 h	4.6	0.025	Capacity	
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min				
			Discharge	CC	0.1	10 h	2.8			Register capacity
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min				
Check-up	25	3	Charge	CCCV	0.05	20 h	4.6	0.025	IR	
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min				
			Discharge	CC	0.1	2.5 h	25% SOD			
			Discharge	CC	0.2	30 sec				
			Rest	Open circuit		30 sec				
			Discharge	CC	0.1	2.5 h	50% SOD			
			Discharge	CC	0.2	30 sec				
			Rest	Open circuit		30 sec				
Discharge	CC	0.1	2.5 h	75% SOD						

			Discharge	CC	0.2	30 sec				
			Rest	Open circuit		30 sec				
			Discharge	CC	0.1	2.5 h	2.8			
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min				
Check-up	25	4	Charge	CC	0.05	6 h	3.9		Self discharge	
			Rest	Open circuit		24 h				
			Discharge	CC	0.1	10 h	2.8			
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min				
Charge 30% SOC	25	5	Charge	CCCV	0.05	6 h		0.025	SOC30 – cap check	
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min				

WP5_M4: charging protocol from 30% to 100 % SOC for LCC/Li-rich NMC cells

WP	WP5
Cell type	LCC/ Li-rich NMC
Cell format	MLPC
Protocol	WP5_M4

Charge from 30% to 100 % SOC

Stage	T, oC	Step	Mode	Control Current, C	Termination conditions			Cycles		
					Time	Voltage, V	Current			
Safety limits						<2.45, >4.9				
Pause	25	0	Rest	Open circuit		12 h				
Residual charge	25	1	Charge	CCCV	0.05	16 h	4.8	0.025	2	
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min				
			Discharge	CC	0.05	20 h	2.8			
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min				
Check-up	25	2	Charge	CCCV	0.05	20 h	4.6	0.025	Capacity	
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min				
			Discharge	CC	0.1	10 h	2.8			
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min				
Check-up	25	3	Charge	CCCV	0.05	20 h	4.6	0.025	IR	
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min				
			Discharge	CC	0.1	2.5 h	25% SOD			
			Discharge	CC	0.2	30 sec				
			Rest	Open circuit		30 sec				
			Discharge	CC	0.1	2.5 h	50% SOD			
			Discharge	CC	0.2	30 sec				

			Rest	Open circuit		30 sec		
			Discharge	CC	0.1	2.5 h	75% SOD	
			Discharge	CC	0.2	30 sec		
			Rest	Open circuit		30 sec		
			Discharge	CC	0.1	2.5 h	2.8	
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min		
Charge 100% SOC	25	5	Charge	CCCV	0.05	20 h	4.6	0.025
			Rest	Open circuit		10 min		